
D3.2 / First report on predictive modelling for PD

Editor

Harris Sotirakis (AUTH)

Contractual delivery

November 2024

Actual delivery

December 2024

Deliverable type

R - Document, report

Dissemination level

PU – Public

Version - date

1.0 - 24/12/2024

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Health and Digital Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable ID

Project acronym	AI-PROGNOSIS
Project full title	Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis
Grant Agreement ID	101080581
Deliverable number	D3.2
Deliverable title	First report on predictive modelling for PD
Work package	WP3 - Predicting PD risk, progression and medication response
Deliverable type	R - Document, report
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Version - date	1.0 - 24/12/2024
Contractual delivery	November 2024
Actual delivery	December 2024
Lead partner	AUTH
Editor	Harris Sotirakis (AUTH)
Contributors	Ioannis Gerasimou, Apostolos Moustaklis, Stelios Hadjidimitriou (AUTH); Kyroula Christodoulou, Paraskevi Chairta, Kyriaki Michailidou (CING); Ali Saad (AING); Christos Chatzichristos (KUL), Thomas Struypstens, Maarten De Vos (KUL); Theodora Brisimi, Petros Dimitrakopoulos (INTRA); Margherita Fabbri (CHUT); Maria Luisa Almarcha Menargues (FIN); Nils Schnalke, Tim Feige (TUD)
Reviewed by	Nikos Grammalidis (CERTH) Nils Schnalke (TUD)
Approved by	Leontios Hadjileontiadis (AUTH, Project Coordinator)
Keywords	Artificial intelligence; biomarkers; dyskinesia; genetics; medication; Parkinson's disease; polygenic risk score predictive modelling; prognostic modelling; progression; risk; side effects; wearables;

Document history

Version	Date	Contributors	Action / status
0.1	20/06/2024	AUTH	Initial document structure (table of contents)
0.2	10/07/2024	AUTH, KUL, CING, INTRA, AING	Final document structure (table of contents); Input to sections 1-9;
0.3	29/11/2024	AUTH, KUL, CING, INTRA, AING	Input to sections 1-9; Sections 5-8 reviewed by clinical partners; Ready for internal review
0.3	12/12/2024	TUD	Reviewed by Nils Schnalke (TUD)
0.3	18/12/2024	CERTH	Reviewed by Nikos Grammalidis (CERTH)
0.4	18/12/2024	AUTH, KUL, CING, INTRA, AING	Document revised
0.5	24/12/2024	AUTH	Minor changes; Approved by the Project Coordinator
1.0	24/12/2024	AUTH	Submitted version

Contents

List of figures	8
List of tables.....	10
List of abbreviations	11
Executive summary.....	14
1 Introduction	15
1.1 Document scope.....	15
1.2 Document structure.....	16
2 Trustworthy AI development.....	16
2.1 Data Preparation.....	17
2.1.1 Data Quality and Bias Mitigation	17
2.1.2 Outlier Detection and Data Sanitization.....	17
2.1.3 Data Privacy	18
2.1.4 Management of Protected Variables	18
2.2 Development & Internal Validation	18
2.2.1 Model Training and Generalization	18
2.2.2 Performance Benchmarking.....	18
2.2.3 Bias Assessment and Fairness.....	19
2.2.4 Explainability and Uncertainty Benchmarking.....	19
2.3 Overarching management and workflow	19
2.3.1 Model and Dataset Reporting	19
2.3.2 Security.....	20
2.3.3 Societal and Environmental Impact.....	20
2.3.4 Auditability and Accountability.....	20
3 Dataset description	20
3.1 PPMI.....	20
3.1.1 Variables.....	21
3.2 Critical Path for Parkinson’s integrated Parkinson’s database.....	22
3.2.1 Description.....	22
3.2.2 Variables.....	22
4 Dataset harmonization and common data model	22
4.1 OMOP as a Common Data Model for AI-PROGNOSIS.....	23
4.2 The PPMI Use-case.....	24
4.2.1 Methodology	24
4.2.2 Data Preprocessing	25
4.2.3 Data Harmonization	26
4.2.4 Data harmonisation module set-up and implementation.....	32
5 Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis.....	33
5.1 Background and Objectives	33
5.2 Methods.....	33
5.2.1 Genetic Datasets	33

5.3	Results.....	35
5.3.1	Genetic datasets.....	35
5.3.2	Genetic analysis	35
5.4	Discussion	41
5.4.1	Interpretation.....	41
5.4.2	Limitations	41
6	Development and evaluation of a model to estimate PD risk.....	42
6.1	Background and objectives	42
6.1.1	Background	42
6.1.2	Objectives.....	42
6.1.3	Implementation	43
6.2	Methods.....	43
6.2.1	Dataset description	43
6.2.2	Data pre-processing.....	44
6.2.3	Prediction models	48
6.2.4	Analytical methods.....	48
6.2.5	Training versus evaluation	49
6.3	Results.....	49
6.3.1	Participants.....	49
6.3.2	Model development.....	50
6.3.3	Model specification	50
6.3.4	Model performance.....	50
6.4	Discussion	57
6.4.1	Interpretation.....	57
6.4.2	Limitations	58
6.4.3	Next steps and future directions.....	58
7	Development and evaluation of a model to predict PD progression.....	59
7.1	Background and objectives	59
7.2	Methods.....	60
7.2.1	Dataset description	60
7.2.2	Data pre-processing.....	60
7.2.3	Prediction models	62
7.2.4	Analytical methods.....	64
7.2.5	Training versus evaluation	65
7.3	Results.....	65
7.3.1	Participants.....	65
7.3.2	Model development.....	67
7.3.3	Model specification	67
7.3.4	Model performance.....	68
7.4	Discussion	71
7.4.1	Interpretation.....	71
7.4.2	Limitations	71
7.4.3	Usability of the model in the context of current care.....	72
8	Development and evaluation of a model to predict side effects related to PD medication	72

8.1	Background and objectives	72
8.2	Methods.....	73
8.2.1	Dataset description	73
8.2.2	Data pre-processing.....	73
8.2.3	Prediction models	74
8.2.4	Analytical methods.....	75
8.3	Results.....	75
8.3.1	Participants	75
8.3.2	Model development.....	75
8.3.3	Model specification	76
8.3.4	Model performance	77
8.4	Discussion	78
8.4.1	Interpretation.....	78
8.4.2	Limitations	79
8.4.3	Usability of the model in the context of current care	80
9	Open science	80
9.1	Data sharing	80
9.2	Code sharing	80
10	Conclusions.....	80
	References	81

List of figures

Figure 4.1 The OMOP Common Data Model.....	23
Figure 4.2 Entity-Relationship diagram of the subset of OMOP used to model PPMI data .	24
Figure 4.3 Flowchart of PPMI variables mapping process to the OMOP CDM.....	27
Figure 4.4 Flowchart of PPMI values mapping process to the OMOP CDM.	30
Figure 5.1 The number of participants/variants before and after the QC analysis in the PPMI datasets. The yellow highlighted font shows the samples that were included.	37
Figure 5.2 PCA plots of the PPMI datasets. PCA plots of (A) NeuroX, (B) Immunochip, (C) 244_LONI and (D) NeuroX Prodromal datasets.	38
Figure 5.3 Manhattan Plots of PPMI datasets (PD cases vs Controls). Manhattan Plots of (A) NeuroX, (B) Immunochip, (C) 244_LONI and (D) NeuroX Prodromal. The assayed SNPs (dots) are sorted by chromosomal locations on the x-axis. The y-axis shows the negative logarithmic p-value of the SNPs.	38
Figure 5.4 PRS (polygenic risk score) distribution between PD (Parkinson’s disease) cases (red line) and controls (blue line), using NEUROX data. This plot shows the probability density versus PRS in cases and controls.....	39
Figure 5.5 PCA plot of the AMP-PD datasets (PD vs HC).	39
Figure 5.6 Manhattan Plots of AMP-PD dataset (PD cases vs Controls). The assayed SNPs (dots) are sorted by chromosomal locations on the x-axis. The y-axis shows the negative logarithm of P-values, and as a result, the higher dots represent significant hits. Blue line indicates the standard p-value and red line indicates the p-value threshold for GWAS.	40
Figure 5.7 PRS (polygenic risk score) distribution between PD (Parkinson’s disease) cases and controls, using AMP-PD data. This plot shows the probability density versus PRS in cases and controls.	40
Figure 6.1 Calculation of an aggregated feature vector using tsfresh package.....	45
Figure 6.2 ROC curve and PRC of the model informed by digital measurements, demographics and somatometrics.....	51
Figure 6.3 Digital risk score grouped by PPMI cohort (PD, Healthy controls and Prodromal). Box plot centre line \equiv median; box limits \equiv upper and lower quartiles; whiskers \equiv $1.5 \times$ IQR; dots \equiv individual predictions; **** $p \leq 1.00e-04$, ns not significant.	51
Figure 6.4 Balanced random forest GINI index-based feature importance of the top 10 features of the PD risk estimation model-based.....	52
Figure 6.5 SHAP values distribution for classes PD vs Healthy controls for digital measurement only model.....	53
Figure 6.6 SHAP values for the top 20 features for the digital measurements only model. .	53
Figure 6.7 Reliability curves of the uncalibrated and calibrated PD risk estimation model ..	54
Figure 6.8 Correlation between the digital score for PD and healthy control population and the minimum putamen SBR	55
Figure 6.9 Correlation between the digital risk score and the MDS PD risk model derived score	55
Figure 6.10 Digital risk score trajectories for the 3 phenoconverters and 8 age-matched healthy controls.....	56
Figure 6.11 SHAP values of the PD risk score model for the phenoconverters.....	57
Figure 6.12 Feature distribution of the phenoconverters compared to PD and healthy controls	57
Figure 7.1 Percentage of males (1) and females (0) in the PD cohort	66
Figure 7.2 Percentage of participants identifies as white (1) and other racial groups (0)	66
Figure 7.3 Box Plot of MDS-UPDRS PART 3 scores by Genetic Subgroup.....	67
Figure 7.4 Box Plot of MDS-UPDRS PART 3 scores by Age Range	67
Figure 7.5 Actual vs. predicted UPDRS total scores at visit 04 using BL data	69

Figure 7.6 Actual vs. predicted UPDRS total scores at visit 04 using BL + visit 02 data	69
Figure 7.7 Feature importance for baseline features	70
Figure 7.8 Feature importance for baseline + visit 02 (BL+V02) features	70
Figure 8.1 Subject participation and dyskinesia occurrence for the two CPP datasets currently under analysis. Both graphs only include subjects whose dyskinesia status was reported in the dataset.....	76
Figure 8.2 PD-1000, per visit paradigm	77
Figure 8.3 PD-1000, per visit paradigm	77
Figure 8.4 PD-1003, per visit paradigm	77
Figure 8.5 PD-1003, per visit paradigm	77
Figure 8.6 PD-1000, per-subject paradigm.....	78
Figure 8.7 PD-1000, per-subject paradigm.....	78
Figure 8.8 PD-1003, per-subject paradigm.....	78
Figure 8.9 PD-1003, per-subject paradigm.....	78

List of tables

Table 4.1 Example of conditions grouping and mapping.....	28
Table 4.2 Examples of medication grouping and mapping.....	29
Table 4.3 Examples of questionnaires total scores	31
Table 5.1 Genotypes Frequencies and Association of 17 SNPs with PD Under Logistic Regression Analysis in MJF dataset (Patients with PD Versus Healthy Controls)	35
Table 6.1 Description of the pre-calculated Verily features available in the PPMI used in the PD risk prediction model	44
Table 6.2 MDS PD risk and prodromal markers.....	46
Table 6.3 Description of novel features extracted for PD risk prediction model based on Verily study raw sensor data	48
Table 6.4 PD risk dataset description	49
Table 6.5 Performance of each model version in estimating PD risk. Demographics refer to Sex & Age and somatometrics include Height & Weight	50
Table 7.1 Percentage of missing values for MDS-UPDRS PART3 across visits in the PPMI dataset.....	60
Table 7.2 Summary of indicators identified from the PPMI dataset for PD progression model development	62
Table 7.3 Summary of the selected features and their definitions	63
Table 7.4 Summary of Age at Enrolment, Age at Visit, and Years of Education Among PD Participants.....	66
Table 7.5 Summary of Neural Network and Random Forest model architectures for Predicting PD Progression.....	68
Table 7.6 Model performance for predicting MDS-UPDRS part 3 (MDS-UPDRS PART 3) score at visit 04.....	69
Table 8.1 Participation and dyskinesia statistics for each dataset and prediction framework	76
Table 8.2 Hyperparameter search space for the dyskinesia prediction RF model.	76

List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
AI-PMP	AI-based progression and medication response prediction study
AI-PRA	Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's risk assessment study
AMP-PD	Accelerating medicines partnership – Parkinson's disease
AUC	Area under the curve
BL	Baseline
BRFC	Balanced random forest classifier
CDM	Common data model
COMT	Catechol-O-methyltransferase
CPP	Critical Path for Parkinson's
CSF	Cerebro-spinal fluid
DAT	Dopamine transporter imaging
dBM	Digital bio-marker
EDA	Exploratory data analysis
ESS	Epworth sleepiness scale
GBA	Glucosylceramidase Beta
GDS	Geriatric depression scale
GWAS	Genome-wide association study
HC	Healthy controls
IDA-LONI	Image and data archive at the laboratory of neuroimaging
LLRK2	Leucine-rich repeat kinase 2
LOINC	Logical observation identifiers names and codes
LOSO	Leave one subject out
MAE	Mean absolute error
MDS	Movement disorder society
ML	Machine learning
MSE	Mean squared error

NaN	Not a number
NN	Neural networks
NS-PARK	French clinical research network for PD
OHDSI	Observational health data sciences and informatics
OMOP	Observational medical outcomes partnership
PCA	Principal component analysis
PD	Parkinson's disease
PET	Positron emission tomography
PPMI	Parkinson's progression markers initiative
PR-AUC	Precision-recall area under the curve
PRC	Precision-recall curves
PRS	Polygenic risk score
QC	Quality check
QUIP	Questionnaire for impulsive-compulsive disorders in Parkinson's disease–rating scale
RBD	REM behaviour disorder
ReLU	Rectified linear unit
REM	Rapid eye movement
RF	Random forest
RMSE	Root mean squared error
ROC	Receiver operating characteristic curve
RxNorm	RxNorm (normalized names for clinical drugs)
SBR	Striatal binding ratio
SCOPA-AUT	Scales for outcomes in Parkinson's disease - autonomic dysfunction
SNCA	Synuclein alpha gene
SNOMED CT	Systematized nomenclature of medicine - clinical terms
SNP	Single nucleotide polymorphism
SOA	State of the art
SQL	Structured query language

TRIPOD	Transparent reporting of a multivariable prediction model for individual prognosis or diagnosis
UKBB	United Kingdom biobank
UPDRS	Unified Parkinson's disease rating scale
UPSIT	University of Pennsylvania smell identification test
WES	Whole exome sequencing
WGS	Whole genome sequencing

Executive summary

The deliverable D3.2 provides an overview of all methodologies, findings and future directions of the AI-PROGNOSIS predictive models for Parkinson's disease (PD). The deliverable focuses on three main pillars of prognostic modelling: a) estimation of the risk of developing PD, b) estimation of progression in PD, and c) estimation of response to medication. Hence, three distinct modelling approaches are presented, following the TRIPOD+AI reporting guidelines. The models use multimodal data, including sociodemographic factors, wearable device data and genetic profiles from wealthy, open large-scale datasets, such as the PPMI and AMP-PD. Pre-modelling achievements of the project include the successful harmonization of the core dataset using the observational medical outcomes partnership (OMOP) common data model, as well as efficient data pre-processing, such as bias mitigation, outlier detection, data imputation to improve model robustness, generalizability and fairness. Challenges were faced and addressed to ensure seamless data harmonisation, paving the way for harmonising datasets to be accessed in the future.

The results of the three distinct analyses show the potential of the predictive models to accurately identify PD risk, track its progression and evaluate the adverse effects associated with PD medication. Genetic analysis revealed several Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNPs) that are significantly associated with PD; however, we observed some heterogeneity, highlighting the need for more data and further subgroup analyses to refine Polygenic risk score (PRS) predictions. Digital biomarkers, derived from wearable devices in the Verily study, are valuable in distinguishing people with PD from healthy controls, highlighting their potential to constitute a complementary tool to conventional clinical examinations. The development of PD progression models demonstrated a potential to predict one-year progression when incorporating longitudinal data (PPMI dataset) by integrating baseline metrics and follow-up progression for more accurate prognosis. Further, predictive models for side effects due to PD treatment achieved a promising accuracy in predicting dyskinesias, considering the levodopa dosage, time since diagnosis and Catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT) inhibitors as important contributing factors. Nonetheless, dataset heterogeneity, missing data (values, metrics or cases), and the complex nature of the high-dimensional datasets, render the modelling task challenging. For this reason, the AI-PROGNOSIS project aims to identify and access more datasets to further validate the current report's findings. Further, key principles of trustworthy AI focusing on fairness, transparency and ethical considerations have already been developed in AI-PROGNOSIS and were or will be considered throughout the final stages of model development.

The AI-PROGNOSIS predicting modelling for PD effort represents all critical steps taken towards the development and evaluation of accurate and robust models for estimating PD risk, progression and response to medication. Such approaches will ensure a seamless integration of advanced and novel AI-driven solutions, into clinical practice and PD management.

1 Introduction

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a complex and progressive neurodegenerative disorder that affects ~6.2 million individuals globally¹, with 1.2 million of them residing in Europe². PD diagnosis and monitoring are significantly challenging due to the broad range of motor and non-motor symptoms. There is currently no cure for PD, and the dopaminergic medication is used mainly for managing symptoms. This highlights the necessity for advanced predictive models that can aid in screening, prognosis and estimation of the effects of PD treatment regimes.

Digital biomarkers (dBM) are revolutionizing the landscape of neurodegenerative disorders including PD by analysing large-scale, multisource retrospectively collected datasets such as the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI)³, the UK Biobank (UKBB)⁴ and the (C-Path)⁵. Such datasets include in-depth clinicodemographic, imaging, genetic (Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms; SNPs that can be combined into Polygenic Risk Scores; PRSs), wearable sensor data and other datasets, longitudinally collected, constituting useful resources for developing models that can offer insights for the disease manifestation and management.

Machine learning and Artificial intelligence (ML/AI) algorithms have been applied to multisource data with the ultimate aim of developing robust biomarkers (for an extensive review, refer to *D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets*). Previous work has demonstrated that the analysis of clinicodemographic, imaging, genetics and wearable data can predict the PD onset seven years before its first clinical diagnosis, promising a valuable tool for the disease management (Schalkamp et al., 2023). Machine learning has also been used in studies aiming to develop new biomarkers for specific symptoms, such as bradykinesias (Iakovakis et al., 2018), to track the disease progression (Severson et al., 2021; Sotirakis et al., 2023), while the utility of ML to estimating the response to medication in people with PD, remains widely unexplored. Analysing large datasets allows us to discover patterns and identify key risk factors contributing to the development of the disease.

1.1 Document scope

This deliverable aims to collectively present all methodologies and results from AI-PROGNOSIS research on predictive modelling in PD following a novel, trustworthy and inclusive approach to AI model development. The model development and evaluation report (Sections 6-8) follows the TRIPOD-AI guidelines⁶. The developed models will be externally validated in the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical studies (AI-PRA and AI-PMP). For the purposes of this deliverable, we analysed data from open, multimodal datasets (PPMI and AMP-PD) to develop and evaluate three models, namely, the PD risk prediction model, the PD progression model and the PD response to medication model. • **PD risk estimation:** aims to estimate the risk of developing PD, classifying between people with PD and healthy controls (HC) using a rich dataset collected with the Verily study watch⁷ alongside detailed clinicodemographic information from the PPMI study. The model outcomes are validated using clinical and DaT-scan ground truth variables. • **PD progression estimation:** the PPMI comprehensive longitudinal dataset was used to develop novel biomarkers to predict the progression of clinical

¹ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6311367/>

² <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6191528/>

³ <https://www.ppmi-info.org>

⁴ <https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk>

⁵ <https://c-path.org>

⁶ <https://www.bmj.com/content/385/bmj-2023-078378>

⁷ <https://verily.com/perspectives/introducing-verily-study-watch>

symptoms in 12 months using baseline data. • **PD response to medication:** as individual responses to PD medication can vary, our predictive models aim to identify the factors that influence treatment adverse effects with an initial exploration on dyskinesia side effects • **Genetic analysis:** PRS per individual are calculated with the overall aim to be provided as input to the modelling process and will be used as one of the predictors of PD risk, disease progression and response to medication at a later stage. • To ensure robust, reliable and clinically meaningful predictions, this deliverable also addresses the integration of **trustworthy AI principles** and **dataset harmonization strategy** into developing the predictive models.

D3.2 is the outcome of the tasks T3.3 *Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis*, T3.4 *PD risk predictive modelling*, T3.5 *PD progression predictive modelling* and T3.6 *Medication response predictive modelling*. It is important to note that D3.2 represents an initial model development report, with D3.4 to follow as the updated and final version of the model report. Hence, the present report not only aims to present all developments associated with predictive modelling for PD but also to set the ground for further advances and clear future directions in the field.

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable provides a comprehensive report of predictive modelling in PD, structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction, including the theoretical background
- Section 2 covers the essential aspects of developing reliable AI models, including data preparation, model development and validation and overall management and workflow
- Section 3 outlines the datasets used, their content and relevance to PD research
- Section 4 addresses the strategies for data harmonisation, including the application of OMOP common data model
- Section 5 presents the genetic profiling techniques and methods, including the background and detailed analysis of various genetic datasets.
- Section 6 details the methodology and findings related to developing and evaluating a model for estimating the risk of developing PD
- Section 7 outlines the development and evaluation of a model to predict PD progression
- Section 8 focuses on modelling the responses to PD medication, focusing on potential adverse effects
- Section 9 provides details on open science practices
- Section 10 summarises key findings, implications and future direction recommendations based on the conducted research

2 Trustworthy AI development

While developing predictive models PD involving progression, risk assessment, medication response, and genetic profiling—our focus remains on adhering to key principles of Trustworthy AI. This ensures that our models are robust, fair, and transparent while maintaining high standards for data quality, privacy, and societal responsibility. This section reflects our commitment to the principles and guidelines established in *D2.2 Trustworthy AI Development and Evaluation Framework*. Here, we have highlighted specific AI development steps where Trustworthy AI principles—such as data integrity, bias mitigation, transparency, and accountability—are already implemented. Notably, the PD risk model presented in this

deliverable has been developed under the trustworthy AI framework. During development, PD progression and medication response models have also adopted key trustworthy AI principles. Further enhancements are planned for the final versions to ensure full alignment with a trustworthy AI framework.

2.1 Data Preparation

2.1.1 Data Quality and Bias Mitigation

Each model underwent rigorous data quality assessments tailored to its domain, ensuring the reliability and integrity of the datasets used.

- **Genetic Profiling for PD Risk Assessment (CING):** Genetic data quality was assessed using standard thresholds in genetic association studies, such as call rates (<95%), Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) ($p < 10^{-5}$), and minor allele frequency (<1%). Samples and SNPs failing these thresholds were excluded, ensuring robust genetic and statistical analyses.
- **PD risk prediction (AUTH):** Exploratory data analysis (EDA) was conducted to assess data quality. Missing values were imputed where possible, while incomplete or low-variance columns were discarded. For time-series data, only contiguous bouts devoid of gaps were analysed, and preprocessing steps validated schema compliance, addressing possible recording and sampling errors.
- **PD Progression Modelling (AING):** Completeness checks, imputation strategies, and complete case analysis were employed to manage missing data and standardize the dataset.
- **Medication Response Modelling (KUL):** Manual inspection of data fields was performed to correct impossible values and account for misspelt entries using fuzzy string matching. This ensured consistency by standardizing similar entries.

Across all models, fairness considerations and bias mitigation strategies were adopted or planned:

- **Demographic analysis** was conducted to identify potential imbalances (AING, AUTH).
- **Covariate adjustments** were applied for genetic analyses (CING).
- **Feature importance metrics** were analyzed to identify over-reliance on specific features in the PD risk and the medication response model, with plans for re-training while penalizing these biases (AUTH, KUL).
- **Fairness metrics and tools**, such as IBM Fairness 360, are planned to be implemented in future iterations across all models for quantitative assessments of biases.

2.1.2 Outlier Detection and Data Sanitization

Standardised statistical techniques were employed across models to detect and handle outliers, ensuring the datasets were representative and accurate for analysis. Outlier detection was embedded within the quality control process for the genetic profiling for PD risk assessment, using thresholds for SNPs and samples. In the PD risk model, outliers in accelerometer data were detected using z-scores and distribution analysis. No significant outliers were found for tabular data after reviewing distribution metrics

Statistical methods, including z-score thresholds ($z = 3$), were implemented for the PD progression model to identify and address outliers. For the medication response modelling, the abovementioned z-score threshold was applied.

Data sanitization was generally not required for the datasets used across models, as they were either pre-sanitized or already pseudonymised and stored securely.

2.1.3 Data Privacy

All datasets were pre-anonymized or pseudonymised at the source (e.g., PPMI and AMP-PD repositories), and participant identities were safeguarded across models. This ensures privacy by removing any identifying information during data collection and analysis.

2.1.4 Management of Protected Variables

The key protected variables identified for PD models, validated by AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts, include:

- **Age:** Influences PD risk and progression, with older individuals at higher risk.
- **Gender:** Men are statistically more likely to develop PD than women.
- **Level of Education:** Socioeconomic factors like education level can influence disease awareness and healthcare access.
- **Family History:** A family history of PD suggests a genetic predisposition.
- **Ethnicity:** Certain ethnic groups (e.g., Basque, Jewish populations) may have higher genetic links to PD.
- **Location:** Geographical location influencing environmental exposures, healthcare, lifestyle
- **Occupation:** The type of occupation and its associated physical and mental stress levels

At a later stage of the project, these protected variables will be tracked, anonymised, and incorporated selectively to ensure fairness without compromising privacy. This will allow for model validation across demographic lines, which is especially critical for fairness assessments in the progression and medication models. This crucial step will be implemented in the *Final report on predictive modelling for PD (D3.4)*.

2.2 Development & Internal Validation

2.2.1 Model Training and Generalization

Model training employed robust techniques across tasks to ensure generalization and reduce overfitting. For PD risk, model training was performed using a Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation scheme. Standard scaling (z-score normalization) was applied to each feature during training for each fold to ensure consistent scaling. Furthermore, for the PD progression model, five-fold cross-validation was implemented, with batch normalization and dropout layers incorporated to prevent overfitting. As for the medication response, models were trained using stratified 10-fold cross-validation to ensure the training and validation datasets contained disjoint subject sets, preventing overfitting. Pooling data from multiple datasets ensures a diverse cohort, further enhancing generalizability.

External validation on independent datasets, such as the UK Biobank (UKBB), is a shared priority across all models and will be implemented in the upcoming *D3.4 Final report on predictive modelling for PD*. These efforts will ensure the models generalize well across diverse populations and data collection settings.

2.2.2 Performance Benchmarking

Performance benchmarks were established based on clinical standards, existing models, and key outcome measures, with specific metrics employed across models to ensure robust evaluation:

- **PD Risk Model:** Benchmarks included ground truth decisions by clinicians, namely the MDS risk model for PD risk assessment and minimum putamen SBR values. Classification metrics such as precision, accuracy, sensitivity, F1-score, ROC-AUC and PR-AUC were utilized to evaluate model generalization and predictive accuracy. The concordance index (C-index) will be used in the updated version of the model to assess the generalisation of model predictions.
- **PD Progression Modelling:** The Movement disorders society – Unified Parkinson’s disease rating scale (MDS-UPDRS) Part 3 score was used as the benchmark for PD progression, reflecting motor symptom severity. Performance metrics included mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), MAE, R², and Pearson Correlation, providing a comprehensive assessment of predictive accuracy.
- **Medication Response Modelling:** Benchmarks were derived from a literature review, offering approximate performance expectations based on similar studies. Metrics included area-under-curve (AUC) of the ROC curve, which was used to maintain a balance between sensitivity and specificity for binary classification (e.g., predicted side-effect or no side-effect).

2.2.3 Bias Assessment and Fairness

Bias and fairness assessments will be reinforced in the final version of the PD predictive models with fairness libraries (e.g., IBM Fairness 360), focusing on statistical parity and potential biases for each demographic group. Sample weighting, covariate adjustments, and resampling will be applied across models to manage demographic imbalances.

2.2.4 Explainability and Uncertainty Benchmarking

Models such as Random Forest in PD medication response and in PD progression model inherently provide explainability through feature importance analysis. For the PD risk model, GINI index-based feature importance and SHAP values⁸ were computed to analyze feature contributions. Future enhancements involve post-hoc methods like Shapley values for non-explainable models, which are derived from cooperative game theory and attribute the contribution of each feature to the model's prediction by distributing the prediction outcome fairly among all features. This ensures interpretability by showing how each feature influences individual predictions. Additionally, uncertainty quantification frameworks (e.g., Uncertainty Quantification 360) will be used to establish prediction confidence, particularly in PD risk assessment.

2.3 Overarching management and workflow

2.3.1 Model and Dataset Reporting

Transparency and comprehensive reporting were prioritized to ensure reproducibility and adherence to best practices. All predictive modelling sections (Sections 6,7,8) followed the TRIPOD checklist⁹ to ensure transparent reporting of dataset characteristics, pre-processing and modelling approaches. Further, the medication response modelling follows internal KU Leuven guidelines, ensuring detailed documentation and reproducibility for authorized users of the datasets. Across all tasks, reporting practices adhere to institutional and project-specific standards, with ongoing improvements to maintain clarity, transparency, and reproducibility in future deliverables.

⁸ <https://shap.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁹ <https://www.bmj.com/content/385/bmj-2023-078378>

2.3.2 Security

Data and model security were maintained with encryption, firewall protection, SSH certificate access, and secure storage. Institutional guidelines and limited access further safeguard data integrity and protect against unauthorized access across all models.

2.3.3 Societal and Environmental Impact

The developed models have significant potential to enhance personalized PD care and management, leading to better health outcomes and improved quality of life for patients. For medication response modelling, the primary socio-ethical impact lies in identifying individuals at higher risk of medication side effects, enabling more personalized and safer prescription practices. Similarly, the PD risk and progression models aim to refine personalized care pathways.

From an environmental perspective, the lightweight nature of the models minimizes their computational impact. Moreover, further efforts are planned to optimize resource use and explore eco-friendly infrastructure options.

2.3.4 Auditability and Accountability

Mechanisms for auditability and accountability have been implemented across tasks to ensure transparency, traceability, and reliability in the development process. For medication response modelling, tight version control is maintained through GitHub, accompanied by a logging system to track model performance metrics across different subsets of data and versions. Similarly, for PD risk and progression modelling, all source code is version-controlled, with datasets treated as immutable objects. Instead of directly versioning data, the processing pipelines are versioned to ensure reproducibility (refer to Section 9.2 for code sharing). Monitoring is performed during model training, and models reported in deliverables are saved for further validation and analysis.

3 Dataset description

This section outlines the datasets accessed and used for the training and evaluating the three predictive models. A full list of the datasets accessed for the purposes of AI-PROGNOSIS is presented in the deliverable *D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets*. A list of the datasets and variables used particularly for the genetics analysis is outlined in 5 Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis.

3.1 PPMI

PPMI is a large multi-site observational clinical study running since 2010. It is designed to identify biomarkers of PD progression. The PPMI study is primarily funded by the Michael J Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research. The study is registered at clinicaltrials.gov under the identification number *NCT01141023*. It collects multisource (i.e., clinical, imaging, biospecimen and digital) data from individuals with PD, individuals at risk of developing PD, and healthy controls, rendering the collected data freely available upon reasonable request to research organisations. In total, the PPMI site collaborates with around 50 clinical sites from 12 countries to collect data and bio-samples. Ethical oversight is provided by the institutional review boards at each participating site, and participants provide informed consent for collecting and using their data. Further, the PPMI dataset includes data collected with the Verily study watch, captured between 2018 and 2020. The Verily study watch is a wearable

device designed for clinical research, capable to continuously monitor digital health metrics. It captures – among others – various kinematic data, providing researchers with high quality, longitudinal insights into disease progression.

Therefore, PPMI served AI-PROGNOSIS as a critical source of data for developing models to:

- a) estimate the risk of developing PD,
- b) predict the progression of its symptoms and
- c) estimate the response to dopaminergic medication.

PPMI definitions and descriptions available on the PPMI user guide¹⁰. In brief, the dataset includes the following cohorts (November 2023):

1227 People diagnosed with PD	Participants diagnosed with PD
1233 People with prodromal PD	Participants with REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) or Hyposmia or carrying particular genetic mutations such as GBA or LRRK2.
249 Healthy Controls	Age and sex-matched participants with no PD or any known risk factors to developing PD
3 Scans without dopaminergic deficit (SWEDD)	Participants were diagnosed with clinical PD symptoms but showed normal DaT-scan images. This group is excluded from any analysis presented in this deliverable.

Participants underwent repeated assessments over around five years to track the progression of PD. Participants are clinically assessed every 6 months, whilst the first few visits are typically more frequent.

3.1.1 Variables

PPMI includes important data for developing predictive models, such as:

- Clinical assessments such as demographics, motor and non-motor symptoms.
- Imaging data such as magnetic resonance imaging, DaT-scan and Positron Emission Tomography (PET).
- Biospecimens such as blood samples for genetic and proteomic analysis, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) as well as urine and saliva samples.
- Continuous kinematic data captured over a 2-year period (2018-2020) under the Verily study.

PPMI database is continuously updated. The current report was based on data downloaded from the PPMI portal¹¹ in November 2023.

The selection of the features used to train each of the three distinct models (PD risk, progression and response to medication) was based on 3 distinct sources: a) an extensive state of the art (SoA) review (please refer to deliverable *D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets*), b) a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (KCL, FIN, CHUT, TUD), and c) PPMI data availability.

¹⁰ <https://www.ppmi-info.org/sites/default/files/docs/PPMI%20Data%20User%20Guide.pdf>

¹¹ <https://ida.loni.usc.edu/login.jsp>

3.2 Critical Path for Parkinson's integrated Parkinson's database

3.2.1 Description

In addition to the PPMI, we also employed the Critical Path for Parkinson's (CPP) integrated Parkinson's database¹² for the medication predictive modelling of the Section 8. This integrated database contains diverse clinical trials and observational studies, including a subset of the previously discussed PPMI dataset. These datasets each vary in number of subjects, inclusion criteria, PD stages, age, medication, etc. In total, the Integrated Database contains data of over 12000 subjects from 22 studies. The ultimate aim is to integrate as many of these datasets as possible in the model design, ensuring broad applicability and generalizability. In addition, the variety of sociodemographic and socioeconomic groups included in these datasets reduces the risk of bias and unfairness. Proper clearance for access to the CPP dataset was requested and granted by the CPP according to the outlined [terms and conditions](#).

3.2.2 Variables

The CPP dataset contains a large number of variables, but not all of them are present in every dataset. These variables broadly fall into the following categories:

- Adverse events
- Medical history of associated persons
- Clinical events with diagnostic value (e.g. bradykinesia, tremors, rigidity, gait disturbances, etc.), dopaminergic events (dyskinesia's, dystonia's, freezing, etc.).
- Concomitant medication and their levodopa equivalent dosage, dosage, dosage frequency etc.
- Demographic features: age, sex, race, ethnicity.
- Functional tests: MoCa, Semantic fluency, neurological testing, SCOPA-COG.
- Laboratory results: Blood haematology, urinalysis, etc.
- Medical history
- Nervous system findings
- Physical examinations
- Pharmacogenomics: SNPs for multiple genes of interest (e.g., COMT, GBA, LRRK2)
- Questionnaires: (MDS-)UPDRS, Hoehn and Yahr stage, etc.
- Substance usage: alcohol, caffeine, smoking, etc.
- Vital signs: Heart rate, blood pressure, height, weight, etc.

4 Dataset harmonization and common data model

Before proceeding to further analysis and model training, it is crucial to transform data into a common data model. The harmonization process of various datasets used within AI-PROGNOSIS into a common data model involves transforming and standardizing these diverse data sources into a unified structure with consistent formats, terminologies, and mappings, ensuring compatibility for cross-study analysis and interoperability. This procedure will form a common ground and provide the same definitions of key concepts and terms for all partners of the consortium.

¹² <https://c-path.org/tools-platforms/integrated-parkinsons-database/>

4.1 OMOP as a Common Data Model for AI-PROGNOSIS

“Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership” (OMOP) is a common data model (CDM) aiming to standardize the structure and content of observational healthcare¹³ (**Figure 4.1**). The OMOP CDM is designed to fit a wide range of healthcare data, including electronic health records, insurance claims, clinical trial data, and patient registries. It accommodates diverse data types such as demographic information, diagnoses, procedures, medications, laboratory results, and observational data from various healthcare systems. The model is maintained by the “Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics” (OHDSI)¹⁴ organization. With its wide global adoption, especially in observational health research and real-world evidence studies, OMOP is instrumental in enhancing data interoperability across different systems and studies, facilitating more robust and systematic analysis of clinical data.

Figure 4.1 The OMOP Common Data Model¹⁵

OMOP’s architecture includes 39 tables (37 primary + 2 metadata tables) and is mostly person-centric, as all data are directly or indirectly related to a person (an entry in the ‘Person’ table). Other key tables, such as ‘Visit’, ‘Observation’, ‘Measurement’ and ‘Drug Exposure’, try to model the patient’s interaction with healthcare systems and clinical trials, which is a crucial part of the detailed analysis of data.

The OMOP common data model supports using several standardized medical vocabularies to standardise health-related terms and concepts. These vocabularies ensure consistency in data interpretation across different datasets and data processors. All vocabularies and their content are available to browse and download in the ATHENA¹⁶ portal, a web-based tool allowing users to search, browse, and map healthcare data to OMOP’s unified terminologies.

¹³ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

¹⁴ <https://www.ohdsi.org>

¹⁵ <https://ohdsi.github.io/CommonDataModel>

¹⁶ <https://athena.ohdsi.org/search-terms/start>

Leveraging the power of OMOP CDM will significantly enhance data interoperability and integration in AI-PROGNOSIS. This standardization process ensures consistent and accurate data analysis and facilitates the research process by eliminating complexities associated with data management. The structured format of the OMOP common data model supports efficient querying and aggregation of data, enabling the consortium partners to focus on deriving meaningful insights instead of managing data discrepancies.

Finally, the large and active support community of OHDSI, the creator of OMOP, along with the detailed and up-to-date documentation, provide useful resources for technical guidance, ensuring that the use of OMOP is both strategic and effective for achieving the AI-PROGNOSIS goals.

4.2 The PPMI Use-case

4.2.1 Methodology

Our first step in harmonizing datasets into the OMOP CDM was to work with the PPMI dataset. Serving as a pilot, PPMI guided the refinement and documentation of a methodology for aligning its data—and those of other datasets that will be included in the future—into the OMOP CDM. This work was conducted along two parallel strands: identifying relevant PPMI variables for AI model training and performing an extensive EDA to uncover and address real-world data challenges.

The first strand of work focused on identifying all PPMI variables valuable for AI model training. These variables were selected and validated in close collaboration between clinical partners and AI model developers to ensure clinical relevance and utility for predictive modelling. For each chosen variable, two essential mapping exercises were carried out. First, the OMOP CDM tables that best represent each variable were determined. The Entity-Relationship diagram (**Figure 4.2**) shows the subset of OMOP tables and relationships mostly used to model the PPMI data.

Figure 4.2 Entity-Relationship diagram of the subset of OMOP used to model PPMI data

Then, the ATHENA portal was used to identify standardized OMOP concepts that could capture the meaning of these variables, ensuring alignment with OMOP's terminologies. This mapping process was iterative, with validation from both clinical partners and AI model developers, helping ensure that the variables were accurately and meaningfully integrated into the CDM.

The second strand involved conducting a thorough EDA on the PPMI dataset. As expected, the EDA revealed several challenges when working with real-world data, including data inconsistencies and missing values. Addressing these issues required a collaborative approach with our clinical partners, who provided essential context about the PPMI study design, pre-existing assumptions, and potential approaches for managing data inconsistencies. This effort informed a series of preprocessing steps that refined our harmonization process, establishing a more robust data transformation and mapping approach.

Together, these two strands—variable identification and extensive data exploration—formed the basis of the harmonization methodology. Each preprocessing and harmonization step derived from this work is documented in detail in the following sections, serving as a guide for integrating PPMI and future datasets into the OMOP CDM.

4.2.2 Data Preprocessing

4.2.2.1 Exploratory Data Analysis

The exploratory data analysis (EDA) of the PPMI dataset was conducted to evaluate the quality and consistency of the data before mapping it to the OMOP CDM. This analysis aimed to identify and understand the various issues inherent in the data, which must be addressed as part of the harmonization process. Through EDA, several challenges common in real-world datasets were identified, particularly for data collected over extended periods in clinical research, such as PPMI.

Examples of such challenges include inconsistencies in how the same concept was represented (often due to free-text entries) and instances where information with non-longitudinal character, for example, years of education, appeared to change across different study stages. Also, missing values were encountered, only some of which could be inferred. Finally, another issue that emerged during the exploratory data analysis phase is that some variables were captured at varying levels of detail. Identifying these issues early helped the team design targeted preprocessing steps, described in detail in the following sections.

4.2.2.2 Temporal Alignment

A clear standalone preprocessing step that was performed first was to align PPMI events in time. In the PPMI study, an “event” refers to a specific assessment or data collection point within the patient’s timeline. Events capture various aspects of a participant’s health and can include baseline assessments, follow-up visits, and specialized evaluations. Each event is associated with collected data, such as clinical tests, imaging results, lab measurements, and reported symptoms, representing a snapshot of the participant’s condition at that time. The inconsistency in the events stemmed from the fact that for some cases, the same event for a specific patient appeared in the dataset with different dates, i.e., the same (patient_number, event_id) tuple was associated with two different dates. However, the dates in these cases were found to be closely timed and thus, after validation with the relevant consortium partners, it was assumed that they were recorded to repeat some measurements that are part of the same study visit. Hence, only one date, and specifically the latest, among the multiple dates of the same visit were kept and recorded in OMOP after this preprocessing step.

4.2.2.3 Preprocessing embedded into harmonization steps

Several preprocessing steps have been identified that are embedded within aggregated/combined harmonization tasks rather than functioning as standalone steps (like

e.g. the temporal alignment). For example, diagnoses recorded at varying levels of detail are first aggregated, allowing them to be mapped to the most specific standardized concept available. Similarly, grouping related medication entries into cohesive categories enables the harmonized mapping of these groups to a single standardized medication concept. These integrated preprocessing and harmonization actions ensure consistency and alignment with standardized vocabularies, with each step described in detail in the corresponding harmonization section.

4.2.3 Data Harmonization

4.2.3.1 Mapping of Variables

One of the most central tasks in the harmonization pipeline is that of mapping variables from PPMI tables and entities to standard concepts in the OMOP CDM. Regarding this mapping procedure, two discrete methods were followed.

The first and most straightforward method handled the PPMI variables that already have a directly equivalent column in a relevant OMOP table. This was the case for example for the PPMI variables 'RAINDALS', 'RAASIAN', 'RABLACK', 'RAHAWOPI', 'RAWHITE' and 'RANOS' that are all related to the race of a patient and can be directly mapped to the 'race_concept_id' column of OMOP's 'Person' table. Another variable that exactly matched an OMOP's column is 'SEX' and it was matched to OMOP's table's 'Person' column named 'gender_concept_id'. The values of these columns in OMOP were filled with relevant standard concepts existing in the standardized vocabularies.

The second method handled the cases of PPMI variables that do not have a direct equivalent column in any OMOP table. Most of such variables were modelled through the 'Observation' or 'Measurement' tables of OMOP. The choice between the 'Measurement' or 'Observation' table was performed according to the nature of the data. More specifically, for variables representing quantitative data that are originally obtained via diagnostic/lab tests or instruments (body weight and height, body temperature, blood pressure etc.), the 'Measurement' table was used. Variables that have a more descriptive or qualitative nature, such as socio-economic background (for example years of education), medical history and any other non-numeric data that originate from clinical encounters, are typically mapped to the 'Observation' table of OMOP. The process of the mapping of variables is depicted in **Figure 4.3**.

4.2.3.2 Mapping of Units and Values

The second most important task in the harmonization pipeline is that of mapping a variable's units and values properly into the OMOP CDM. In the PPMI dataset, patients have a value for each variable (except for cases of missing values, the handling of which is discussed below). Depending on the value type (and in some subcases, on the existence of a correspondence between the value and an OMOP concept), we can distinguish the following value mapping processes.

If a value corresponds to a 'Measurement' entry (numerical value), the unit of the numerical value needs to be specified to a unit standard concept existing in one of the standardized vocabularies. Some of the vocabularies used during the PPMI harmonization process are SNOMED¹⁷, LOINC¹⁸ and RxNorm¹⁹. The unit is linked to a measurement through the

¹⁷ <https://www.snomed.org/what-is-snomed-ct>

¹⁸ <https://loinc.org>

¹⁹ <https://mmshub.cms.gov/measure-lifecycle/measure-specification/specify-code/RxNorm>

'unit_concept_id' column of the 'Measurement' OMOP table. The value of the measurement is either specified as a number in the 'value_as_number' field of the OMOP 'Measurement' table or as a standard concept in the 'value_as_concept_id' (in more rare cases, such as medical tests results that have discrete / categorical values, i.e., result of a Sars-CoV-2 antigen test). In the case of PPMI values, no need to use 'value_as_concept_id' was identified to specify the value of a measurement so far. For the case of clinical observations, which is modelled through the 'Observation' table of OMOP, values are again mapped to either a numerical value in the 'value_as_number' field of the OMOP 'Observation' table (for PPMI this applies only to the 'EDUCYRS' variable, which records the years of education of each patient) or to standard OMOP concepts existing in the standardized vocabularies. The latter is the most common for PPMI categorical or qualitative variables mapped to the 'value_as_concept_id' column of the 'Observation' table. To identify the proper OMOP concepts to map values into, the ATHENA portal, which is linked to the OHDSI database for OMOP concepts, was used to efficiently search whether matching concepts exist in the supported standardized vocabularies (SNOMED, LOINC, RxNorm etc.).

Figure 4.3 Flowchart of PPMI variables mapping process to the OMOP CDM.

For PPMI values mapped to the 'value_as_concept_id' column (in either the 'Measurement' or the 'Observation' table) which are not part of the standardized vocabularies that OMOP includes, there appears a need to create custom vocabularies and concepts to include them. Examples of such PPMI values in need for custom concepts include answers to various PD-specific questionnaires, such as the movement disorders society - unified Parkinson's disease rating scale (MDS-UPDRS) ²⁰ or the Scales for Outcomes in Parkinson's disease - Autonomic Dysfunction (SCOPA-AUT) ²¹ questionnaire answers. Details on those questionnaires will also be discussed in following subsections. To define custom concepts, one must first define a custom vocabulary (or vocabularies) that includes them in the relevant OMOP table ('Vocabulary'). Then, the custom concepts are inserted in OMOP's 'Concept' table that links them to a previously defined vocabulary through a foreign key. During the process, it is

²⁰ <https://www.movementdisorders.org/MDS-Files1/Resources/PDFs/MDS-UPDRS.pdf>

²¹ <https://www.movementdisorders.org/MDS/MDS-Rating-Scales/Scales-for-Outcomes-in-Parkinsons-disease---Autonomic-Dysfunction.htm>

important to assign IDs > 2,000,000,000 to the new concepts based on OMOP's guidelines for the definition of new concepts to avoid conflicts with already existing concepts.

The special case of medical conditions – aggregating at the proper level of detail

PPMI also keeps track of patients' medical conditions. To this end, unique conditions identified in the dataset were initially mapped to relevant standard concepts from the SNOMED vocabulary. Then, medical conditions were mapped using the 'Condition_occurrence' and 'Condition_era' OMOP tables.

A relatively challenging part during the mapping process of values was that for some variables the values per patient were recorded at a different level of detail (possibly using free text fields) including more than 9,000 uniquely expressed conditions that were finally mapped to significantly less standard concepts. A typical example of this kind of situation is the case of some records in the "Medical conditions log" table of the PPMI dataset, where for some patients, for example "Eye cataract", was recorded as a medical condition, while for other patients the specific eye that had the condition had been specified ("Left eye cataract", "Right eye cataract" or "Bilateral cataract"). To handle these situations, the universal approach followed was to map each concept to the most specific concept it could be mapped to. This decision was based on the effort to maintain as much of the original variance of data as possible. Thus, for example the value "Eye cataract" was mapped to the SNOMED concept with ID 375545 ("Cataract") while the value "Left eye cataract" was mapped to the SNOMED concept with ID 37311301 ("Cataract of left eye"). However, for many conditions there were many values encountered that could only be mapped to the more general concept. **Table 4.1** tabulates some indicative cases where multiple values of conditions found in the PPMI dataset were mapped to a single standardized concept which is relevant to the conditions.

Table 4.1 Example of conditions grouping and mapping

Standardized concept name	Examples of values encountered	Number of unique values in PPMI records
Spinal arthrodesis (SNOMED)	"L4-I5 spinal fusion", "Spinal fusion", "Spinal fusion (I3-I4)", "Spinal fusion (I3/I4/I5)", "Spinal fusion (I4-I5)", "Spinal fusion from I2-I5", "Spinal fusion I-4-I-5", "Spinal fusion I4/I5", "Had his I4 and I5 fused to help with spinal stenosis."	9
Insertion of stent (SNOMED)	"Stent implantation", "Stent implanted", "Stent in left anterior descending (Iad) artery following cardiac arrest 2014", "Stent in right coronary artery.", "Stent inserted in back of the heart", "Stent placed in 2007 for lower aortic descending artery", "Stent placed in heart", "Stent placed om2", "Stent placement", "Stent placement due to blockage of artery", "2 stents placed", "7 stints in heart",	40

	"Angioplasty and stent placement", "Cardiac stents", "Coronary angioplasty and stents", "Coronary artery blockage, stent placed" ...	
--	--	--

The special case of medications – grouping different forms of expressions

Another special case of the value mapping in the harmonization process is related to the medications. PPMI records the medication (active substance or marketed drug name), the dosage, the frequency, the start and the end date of each treatment. To model these aspects of the PPMI dataset, the OMOP tables 'Drug_exposure' and 'Drug_era' were used. The names of medications were mapped to relevant standard concepts of the RxNorm vocabulary.

However, for some patients, the dosage per tablet for a medication record was specified (i.e., "Carbidopa 25 mg/Levodopa 100 mg"), while for other patients, the dosage per tablet was not specified (i.e., "Carbidopa / Levodopa"). For all medications, grouping was performed, and then each group was mapped to the most specific concept it could be mapped to (similar to the diagnoses). **Table 4.2** lists some indicative medications with multiple values in the PPMI are demonstrated with their corresponding standardized concepts mapped into.

Table 4.2 Examples of medication grouping and mapping

Standardized concept name	Examples of values encountered	Number of unique values in PPMI records
carbidopa 25 / levodopa 100 (RxNorm)	"CARBIDOPA-LEVODOPA 25-100", "CARBIDOPA LEVODOPA 25/100", "CARBIDOPA-LEVODOPA 25/100", "CARBIDOPA/LEVODOPA 25MG/100MG", "CARBIDOPA/LEVODOPA (25/100 MG)", "CARBIDOPA/LEVADOPA (25/100)", "CARBIDOPA /LEVODOPA 25/100", "CARBIDOPA-LEVODOPA 25-100MG", "CARBIDOPA/ LEVODOPA 25/100", "LEVODOPA / CARBIDOPA 100/25", "CARBIDOPA/LEVODOPA 25/100MG TAB", "CARBIDOPA 25MG/LEVODOPA 100MG", "LEVODOPA - CARBIDOPA (100/25)", "LEVODOPA-CARBIDOPA 100/25 MG", "CARBIDOPA/LEVODOPA 25-100 MG", "LEVODOPA CARBIDOPA (100/25 MG)", "LEVODOPA / CARBIDOPA 25/100", "LEVADOPA & CARBIDOPA 100/25", "LEVODOPA-CARBODIPA (100/25)", "LEVODOPA-CABIDOPA 25/100MG", "LEVODOPA/ CARBIDOPA100/25", "L-DOPA 100/25", "CARBIDOPA/LEVODOPA 25/100 IMMEDIATE RELEASE", ...	121
benserazide / levodopa Oral Solution	"LEVODOPA & BENSERAZIDE", "LEVODOPA BENSERAZIDE", "LEVODOPA BENSERAZIDE", "LEDOPODA BENSERAZIDE", "LEVODOPA + BENSERAZIDE",	20

	"LEVODOPA /BENSERAZIDE", "LEVODOPA / BENSERAZIDE", "LEVODOPA/BENSERAZIDE", "LEVODOPA/BENSERAZIDE LP", "Levodopa/Benserazide IR", "LEVODOPA / BENSERAZID", "LEVODOPA BENSERAZID", "LEVODOPA/BENSERACIDE", ...	
--	--	--

Last note in the value mapping step of the harmonization process is the following: another OMOP column that is present in both the 'Observation' and 'Measurement' tables was extensively used, and that is the field named '*_source_value' ('observation_source_value' and 'measurement_source_value' respectively). This field allows to input to OMOP the actual value, exactly as recorded in the PPMI dataset (also known as the "verbatim value"), in a place close to the mapped standardized value of OMOP. This field can be crucial for the data analysis process, as it provides the researchers with a straightforward way to retrieve the raw data, if needed, inside the OMOP common data model. The general process followed (which applies to both measurements and observations) for the mapping of values is visually presented in **Figure 4.4**.

Figure 4.4 Flowchart of PPMI values mapping process to the OMOP CDM.

For all measurements and observations, each entry is linked to the patient through the 'person_id' field which exists in both 'Measurement' and 'Observation' tables. In this way, data processors can retrieve all observations and measurements originating from the original PPMI dataset for each patient of interest.

4.2.3.3 Handling Missing Data

As in all real-world datasets, PPMI is no exception regarding missing values. This was another peculiarity of the data that had to be handled. Specifically, there were cases of variables that included missing values but were considered as mandatory values in the OMOP CDM. Some NOT NULL constraints in the OMOP-SQL schema were dropped for these variables as there was no way to populate them. An example of such variable is the 'BIRTHDT' (date of birth). For cases of missing values for which NOT NULL constraints did not apply in OMOP, the missing values were mapped to relevant "Not available" standard concepts (for the cases that

variables were mapped to exact OMOP columns). In contrast, for the variables that were mapped through the 'Observation' or 'Measurement' tables, the values were simply omitted (no relevant entries were added in the OMOP tables for them).

4.2.3.4 Data Transformations for Compatibility

As expected, there were necessary transformations custom to the PPMI dataset that needed to be applied for the data to be compatible with the OMOP CDM framework. The transformations applied are described below.

The special case of visits

By design, the OMOP data model supports linking each measurement and observation entry to a visit and this ability acts as an indirect way to maintain the order of events when this order is important for a study. To this end, the 'Visit_occurrence' table of OMOP was utilized. For OMOP, an entry in the 'Visit_occurrence' table represents a single encounter of a patient with a health provider in a single point in time (visit occurrences have a date field). However, in PPMI the concept of visit does not exist. Instead, PPMI uses the concept of events to maintain temporal order of encounters of patients with the different stages of the study. Events represent different stages of the study (i.e., Baseline measurement, Screening measurement, 1st visit, 2nd visit etc.) and thus a PPMI event can be related to multiple patients (each patient may participate in the event at different points in time though, according to the time they entered the study). The concept of events is crucial because every measurement and observation in the PPMI dataset is linked to a specific event / phase of the study.

To handle this inherent misalignment between PPMI and OMOP regarding visits and events, the assumption made was that each pairing of a specific patient and event, represented by the (PATNO, EVENT_ID) tuple in PPMI terms, corresponds to a unique occasion when the patient encountered the health providers, who then conducted some measurements or observations for the study. Thus, each unique (PATNO, EVENT_ID) tuple was used to uniquely identify an entry to the OMOP's 'Visit_occurrence' table which is then linked to measurements and observations.

The special case of PPMI questionnaires

A lot of variables of interest identified by the clinicians and the developed AI models (PD risk, PD progression and PD response to medication) included data collected from clinical rating scales and questionnaires. However, after clinical validation with the consortium's partners it was decided that the total scores of specific clinical rating scales will be used instead of the specific items. Hence, itemised scores were aggregated and expressed as a total score reflecting the patient's performance (mostly summing numerical values representing answers to questions included in questionnaires). Examples of such questionnaires and the relevant variables' aggregation can be found in **Table 4.3**.

Table 4.3 Examples of questionnaires total scores

Questionnaire	Number of Individual items (variables)	Custom concept defined to map to the total score
SCales for Outcomes in PArkinson's disease - Autonomic Dysfunction (SCOPA-AUT)	35	SCOPA-AUT Total score
Questionnaire for Impulsive-Compulsive Disorders in	13	QUIP Total score

Parkinson's Disease (QUIP-Current-Short) ²²		
--	--	--

4.2.3.5 Handling different questionnaire versions

During the harmonization process, a significant challenge related to the Movement Disorder Society-Sponsored Revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) appeared. The MDS-UPDRS assessment, published in 2008 and consisting of four parts, is quite an important source of information for Parkinson's patients and comes as a revision of the Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS) originally developed in the 1980s. The PPMI dataset included data in the MDS-UPDRS rating scale, while the OMOP CDM standard concepts only supported the older UPDRS scale. To address this discrepancy in the cleanest way possible and ensure accurate data representation, new custom concepts were defined to capture the specific elements of the newer MDS-UPDRS version found in the PPMI dataset. This approach allowed maintaining the integrity and granularity of the original PPMI data, while ensuring compatibility with the OMOP CDM structure.

4.2.4 Data harmonisation module set-up and implementation

The OMOP CDM is designed as a relational data model, since it organizes healthcare data into a set of related tables (each corresponding to a specific domain), that are linked through keys, allowing data from different domains to be connected and queried relationally. For AI-PROGNOSIS, PostgreSQL has been chosen to meet the project's needs.

The set-up of the harmonization service involves two Docker Compose files. The first Docker Compose file sets up a PostgreSQL server, creates the OMOP CDM schema, loads the standardized vocabularies (LOINC, SNOMED, RxNorm and other OMOP-specific vocabularies, specifically Race and Gender), and starts a pgAdmin service²³ for inspecting and interacting with the database. The DDL scrips for creating the OMOP CDM tables, as well as the script for loading the standardized vocabularies, were provided by the OHDSHI community^{24,25}. The standardized vocabularies were downloaded from the ATHENA portal.

The second Docker Compose file runs the harmonization service, which performs all the preprocessing and harmonization steps described in Sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3. This service is implemented in Python, utilizing extensive data processing libraries such as Pandas²⁶. The preprocessing code saves the pre-processed data into .csv files, which are then read by the harmonization code. The harmonization code generates SQL INSERT statements that can be executed to import the data to the appropriate tables of the OMOP Schema in the PostgreSQL database.

The harmonization service is deployed in a separate machine into Hetzner cloud and will be exposed only to consortium members for them to explore and retrieve the whole set of harmonized data.

²² <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3537263/>

²³ <https://www.pgadmin.org>

²⁴ <https://github.com/OHDSI/CommonDataModel/tree/v5.4.0>

²⁵ <https://github.com/OHDSI/CommonDataModel/tree/v5.3.1/PostgreSQL>

²⁶ <https://pandas.pydata.org>

5 Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis

5.1 Background and Objectives

Although a small percentage of PD (~14%) is familial, most cases are thought to be sporadic and result from a complex interplay between demographics, lifestyle, environmental and genetic factors (Abu Manneh et al., 2022; Skrahina et al., 2021). Age is an important risk factor as the prevalence of PD varies with age. Population studies reported that the genetic background plays a role in triggering the disease. Large-scale Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) have been performed on PD cases and healthy controls and have identified many SNPs that are associated individually with a small risk of developing the disease (Kim et al., 2024; Pitz et al., 2023). These variants, although individually do not contribute to a large increase in the risk of developing PD, can be combined in PRS that has a better predictive performance for a large number of different complex diseases, including PD (Chairta et al., 2021; Nalls et al., 2019).

This task of the AI-PROGNOSIS project aims to extract genetic data from different datasets, perform GWAS and meta-analyses and report the SNPs most significantly associated with the risk of developing PD, its progression and response to dopaminergic medication. The most relevant SNPs will be used to calculate the PRS for each participant and will effectively be used as inputs to the relevant AI prognostic models.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Genetic Datasets

Data from five large-scale biomedical repositories are or will be extracted and analysed. The content of the identified datasets is outlined below.

MJF (Fox Insight)

Fox Insight is an online clinical study building a large, diverse cohort of people with PD and age-matched control volunteers who share information into the lived experience, genetics, and variability of PD. This study includes demographic and genetic data (17 SNPs) of 10252 PD and 458 healthy controls (HC).

PPMI

The PPMI Data Repository, as described in detail in Section 3.1, includes clinical, imaging, 'omics, genetic, sensor, and biomarker data of approximately 1700 participants. Through PPMI, four different datasets with SNP array data were identified.

AMP-PD

AMP- PD gives researchers access to a large, harmonised dataset with common clinical and genomic data, select clinical- and genetic-population information, plus proprietary, research-developed applications for visualising and harmonizing data. This repository includes harmonised data from 8 different studies (10,515 participants).

UK Biobank

The UK Biobank is a large-scale biomedical database and research resource containing de-identified genetic, lifestyle and health information and biological samples from half a million

UK participants. Genetic data include whole genome sequencing (WGS), whole exome sequencing (WES), array genotyping (800,000 genome-wide variants) and imputed genotypes (90 million variants) for approximately 500,000 participants. At the time of this deliverable submission, access to UK Biobank dataset has not been granted; hence more information will be provided in *D3.4 Final report on predictive modelling for PD*.

NS-PARK

The NS-PARK repository includes clinical, biological and imaging data of the PD and healthy control participants. At the time of this deliverable submission, access to NS-PARK dataset has not been granted; hence more information will be provided in *D3.4 Final report on predictive modelling for PD*.

5.2.2 Genetic analysis

Quality check & Imputation

We used standard GWAS quality metrics to ensure the best quality of the genetic results (Marees et al., 2018). Quality control is performed separately within each dataset. Samples with a call rate <95%, as well as SNPs with a call rate <95%, and SNPs not in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium ($P < 10^{-5}$) or with a minor allele frequency <1% were excluded. Principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out for each dataset to assess genetic ancestry and minimize heterogeneity in our data. Imputed data in the same (or compatible) reference panel will be used or generated to facilitate the use of the same SNPs for each dataset and uniform PRS creation. For this step, access to all repositories is requested.

Logistic regression analysis of the three terms

Logistic regression under the log-additive model is used to evaluate all possible associations between the extracted SNPs and PD regarding disease risk.

Bias assessment and mitigation

Duplicate samples involved in more than one study are detected, and the most informative sample is kept for the analysis. Only one SNP of each genomic region will be included in the PRS to avoid biases caused by SNPs in Linkage Disequilibrium.

Polygenic risk score (PRS)

We also constructed PRS to be used for PD risk assessment. The PRS is calculated following the approach previously described by (Mavaddat et al., 2019), which is a score created as a weighted sum of each corresponding risk allele for each individual for the PPMI and AMP-PD datasets. A separate analysis is carried out for each dataset. Three different PRS models were composed by either:

- the most significantly associated SNPs from our analysis,
- the 90 SNPs that are included in the most commonly used PRS study by Nalls M.A *et al.* (2019) or
- the combination of these SNPs.

Ultimately, the SNPs that contribute to a PRS that best discriminates the participant classes will be selected for the predictive model.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Genetic datasets

Noteworthy, during the first semester of the project, the MJF, PPMI, and AMP-PD datasets have already been accessed, analysed and results are reported in the present analysis. The UK Biobank and NS-PARK have been identified, and access has been requested but not yet granted at the time of this deliverable submission.

5.3.2 Genetic analysis

MJF

The MJF dataset includes genotypes of 17 SNPs for 10,252 PD and 458 HC individuals. Despite the small number of SNPs, this dataset consists of many PD cases. Each SNP was analysed for association with PD, and the relevant results are shown in **Table 5.1**. Five out of seventeen SNPs did not pass quality checks (QC). The remaining SNPs were analysed for association with PD, and significant associations of PD with two SNPs were observed in the MJF population at the $p < 0.05$ level. However, none of these associations survive Bonferroni correction for the tests performed ($p=0.004$; based on 12 remaining SNPs).

Table 5.1 Genotypes Frequencies and Association of 17 SNPs with PD Under Logistic Regression Analysis in MJF dataset (Patients with PD Versus Healthy Controls)

		Controls (%)	Cases (%)	HWE	p-value	OR (95% CI)
rs11610045	AA	14.19	19.92	0.17	0.30	1.08 (0.93 - 1.27)
	AG	38.65	41.14			
	GG	19.43	22.55			
rs4698412	AA	29.26	32.62	0.64	0.15	1.1 (0.96 - 1.26)
	AG	50.66	48.71			
	GG	20.09	18.65			
rs823118	CT	39.96	39.81	0.04	-	-
	TT	19.21	28.17			
	CC	13.10	15.62			
rs11658976	AA	25.11	29.09	0.14	0.47	0.94 (0.80-1.11)
	AG	37.34	40.79			
	GG	9.83	13.72			
rs356182	AA	27.29	29.51	0.52	0.16	0.89 (0.76- 1.05)
	AG	34.93	40.17			
	GG	9.61	13.57			
rs2280104	CT	37.12	40.53	0.73	0.72	1.03 (0.88-1.20)
	TT	10.04	11.31			
	CC	31.66	36.74			
rs12456492	AA	38.21	40.66	0.15	0.91	0.99 (0.86-1.15)
	AG	43.01	38.43			
	GG	8.73	10.84			
rs11158026	CT	40.17	40.36	0.97	0.87	0.99 (0.85-1.15)
	TT	9.39	9.40			
	CC	42.58	43.51			
rs9261484	CT	33.41	36.51	0.00	-	-

	TT	5.90	5.36			
	CC	60.70	58.07			
rs10513789	TT	62.88	67.40	0.76	0.03	0.83 (0.71-0.98)
	GT	32.53	29.25			
	GG	4.59	3.35			
rs76904798	CT	17.25	21.52	0.61	0.23	1.15 (0.92-1.45)
	TT	1.09	1.94			
	CC	52.84	59.23			
rs10797576	CT	17.25	20.82	0.91	0.54	1.07 (0.86-1.35)
	TT	1.31	1.80			
	CC	53.71	60.99			
rs2230288	CT	1.31	3.51	0.89	0.01	2.76 (1.34-7.02)
	TT	0.00	0.00			
	CC	97.38	94.46			
rs34637584	AA	0.00	0.06	0.87	0.31	1.47 (0.75-3.42)
	AG	1.53	2.15			
	GG	98.47	97.80			
rs80356773	CT	0.00	0.11	0.00	-	-
	TT	0.22	0.38			
	CC	99.78	99.51			
rs34424986	AA	0.00	0.01	-	-	-
	AG	0.00	0.56			
	GG	99.56	98.99			
i4000415 (rs76763715)	CT	46.94	1.71	0.00	-	-
	TT	53.06	98.24			
	CC	0.00	0.05			

PPMI

The PPMI repository includes four datasets (244_LONI, NeuroX (Project 107), Immunochip and NeuroX_Prodromal) with genetic data. Each dataset includes different numbers of participants as well as different numbers of SNPs as they were genotyped using different arrays. QC analysis was performed separately for each dataset. The numbers of participants/variants before and after the QC analysis are shown in **Figure 5.1**. After the QC, PCA was also performed to explore population stratification among each dataset separately. This analysis illustrates heterogeneity in the population (**Figure 5.2**) as participants were separated into different distinct groups. In the next step, association analysis was carried out using different endpoints (cases vs controls, prodromal vs controls), and the analysis was performed adjusting for 10 principal components to account for population stratification. A large number of variants was assessed, and only a small fraction had a nominal significant p-value ($p < 0.05$). None of the SNPs passed the GWAS threshold (**Figure 5.3**).

Figure 5.1 The number of participants/variants before and after the QC analysis in the PPMI datasets. The yellow highlighted font shows the samples that were included.

In the next step, a PRS was calculated using the SNPs reported in the most commonly used PRS study on PD (Nalls *et al.*, 2019). For this calculation, NeuroX was used because it had the highest number of overlapping SNPs (35 out of 90 SNPs) with the SNPs in the Nalls *et al.* (2019). Logistic regression analysis evidenced that the PRS calculated from these 35 SNPs was not significantly associated with PD ($p = 0.42$) (**Figure 5.4**).

AMP-PD

AMP-PD includes WGS data of 10,417 participants obtained from 8 different studies. Noteworthy, 1,807 out of 10,417 participants are included in both AMP-PD and PPMI datasets; however, they were analysed using a different approach (GWAS for PPMI and WGS for AMP-PD). For the final analyses, AMP-PD data will be used as the AMP-PD repository includes PPMI participants and their whole genome data, which are more informative than GWAS data included in the PPMI repository. AMP-PD participants were divided based on their clinical diagnosis. PD cases (3323) and controls (4133) were included in the QC analysis. After QC analysis, 6710 samples remained (2976 PD cases and 3734 controls) and 1,323,381 SNPs for all chromosomes. Next, PCA analysis was performed, and a significant variation in the AMP-PD population was observed (**Figure 5.5**). Association analysis was carried out between cases vs control, using logistic regression and adjusting for the 10 PCs. This analysis showed that several SNPs are significantly associated with PD, and some of them passed the GWAS threshold ($p < 5 \times 10^{-8}$) (**Figure 5.6**).

PRS was calculated using the SNPs reported by Nalls *et al.* (2019). This calculation included 72 out of 90 SNPs because ambiguous and multiallelic SNPs were excluded. Logistic regression analysis evidenced that the 72 SNPs-PRS is significantly associated with PD ($p = 1.97 \times 10^{-12}$, OR=1.22) (**Figure 5.7**).

Figure 5.2 PCA plots of the PPMI datasets. PCA plots of (A) NeuroX, (B) ImmunoChip, (C) 244_LONI and (D) NeuroX Prodromal datasets.

Figure 5.3 Manhattan Plots of PPMI datasets (PD cases vs Controls). Manhattan Plots of (A) NeuroX, (B) ImmunoChip, (C) 244_LONI and (D) NeuroX Prodromal. The assayed SNPs (dots) are sorted by chromosomal locations on the x-axis. The y-axis shows the negative logarithmic p-value of the SNPs.

Figure 5.4 PRS (polygenic risk score) distribution between PD (Parkinson's disease) cases (red line) and controls (blue line), using NEUROX data. This plot shows the probability density versus PRS in cases and controls.

Figure 5.5 PCA plot of the AMP-PD datasets (PD vs HC).

Figure 5.6 Manhattan Plots of AMP-PD dataset (PD cases vs Controls). The assayed SNPs (dots) are sorted by chromosomal locations on the x-axis. The y-axis shows the negative logarithm of P-values, and as a result, the higher dots represent significant hits. Blue line indicates the standard p-value and red line indicates the p-value threshold for GWAS.

Figure 5.7 PRS (polygenic risk score) distribution between PD (Parkinson's disease) cases and controls, using AMP-PD data. This plot shows the probability density versus PRS in cases and controls.

5.4 Discussion

5.4.1 Interpretation

Up to date, access to three out of five repositories has been granted. QC and association analyses were performed for all the accessible datasets. Although MJF repository includes a relatively large number of PD cases (10,252), the number of overlapping genotyped SNPs (17) is small.

The PPMI repository includes four datasets with genetic data; however, data were obtained through a targeted SNP array method, not WGS. Thus, several of the SNPs used for PRS calculation by Nalls *et al.* (2019) are not included in the PPMI genetic data repository, which was our main data-source. PCA analysis showed that the PPMI population is very heterogeneous, and appropriate adjustments were performed for the association analysis.

Interestingly, PPMI participants are also included in the AMP-PD repository with their WGS data. Therefore, we decided to focus only on the AMP-PD repository for our analysis as it includes participants from eight studies with their whole genome data. Our next step is to explore the ethnicity/ancestry of the participants using their genetic background and divide them into more homogeneous ancestry groups. We expect the PRS to give more significant results with these corrections in identifying people at risk of developing PD.

We intend to use the same data processing procedure for PD progression and medication response predictive models. Logistic regression under log-additive model will be used to evaluate all possible associations between the extracted SNPs and PD in terms of progression and medication response. For PD progression, PD patients will be divided into two groups, fast and slow progression PD (based on MDS-UPDRS). Association analysis will be performed to identify the SNPs that contribute the most to the PD progression rate identification. SNPs could also help in the prediction of an individual's response to certain medication regimes. Therefore, for the medication response predictive modelling, PD patients will be divided into groups based on their response to medication and then association analysis will be performed between the different groups to define the genetic background associated with good or pure response to a drug. The appropriate criteria for classifying the patients into these groups will be decided in close collaboration with the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts.

5.4.2 Limitations

The two main limitations affecting the results of the genetic analysis part are: (1) delays with access to the UK-Biobank, the largest repository planned to be included in this study, and (2) the absence of specific ancestry/ethnicity details of the participants, which may cause a bias in the genetic analysis. These two limitations may decrease the power of these results and may give suboptimal results, which we expect to diminish with the next iteration of our analyses. In addition, data harmonisation across cohorts cannot be performed without access to all requested repositories.

6 Development and evaluation of a model to estimate PD risk

6.1 Background and objectives

6.1.1 Background

PD is often missed or misdiagnosed, as early symptoms are subtle and can be similar to other diseases' manifestations. Early diagnosis enables adequate patient counselling and inclusion of patients in studies with potentially disease-modifying drugs²⁷.

Early and accurate PD risk estimation is crucial for initiating timely and targeted interventions to slow disease progression and improve patient outcomes. To date, scores to estimate PD risk are often limited to specific prodromal PD phase criteria (Berg et al., 2015). In our extensive review of the state of the art (*D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets*), we show that most available models rely on single-modality assessments such as genetic predispositions, demographic factors, or conventional clinical approaches. Clinical examination tools, although useful, are imperfect in the sense that they may fail to capture the complex nature of the disease risk (FitzGerald et al., 2018). ML approaches offer the potential to address these limitations by handling large multi-dimensional and multi-modal datasets that include genomic, clinical, demographic, imaging and kinematic data to achieve a more robust and personalised risk prediction.

- **Sociodemographic factors** play an important role in calculating PD risk. Age, gender, ethnicity, area of living and socioeconomic status not only constitute potential disease predictors, but can also affect access to healthcare resources and, effectively, the timeliness of diagnosis.
- **Wearable sensor (kinematic) data** have become popular in objectively quantifying PD motor and physical activity status that have recently emerged as significant predictors of PD risk (Schalkamp et al., 2023). Sleep disturbance is a common symptom in PD (Menza et al., 2010), and can be captured by wearable devices. Similarly, physical activity, such as walking, reduces the risk of developing PD (Fang et al., 2018) and cadence characteristically increases in individuals with PD (Zanardi et al., 2021).

6.1.2 Objectives

The aim of this section was to develop a PD screening system that integrates unobtrusively collected digital measurements and established clinical and lifestyle-based PD risk markers easily obtainable through questionnaires.

Based on currently available datasets, the *objectives* during this phase of the project were to:

- 1) Develop a model that uses digital measurements of sleep and mobility, with age, sex, weight, and height as covariates, to classify PwPD and healthy controls and produce a digital risk score
- 2) Compare the digital risk score from our model against the current MDS PD risk assessment model in an at-risk cohort.

²⁷ <https://www.lse.ac.uk/business/consulting/assets/documents/the-value-of-early-diagnosis-and-treatment-in-parkinsons-disease.pdf>

6.1.3 Implementation

The following approach was implemented:

Model training: on the digital measurements of sleep and mobility from the Verily study, subset of PPMI.

Model explainability: feature importances were calculated to ensure transparency and clinical interpretability of the results.

Model validation:

- The PD risk digital score was correlated against the score produced by the MDS prodromal and PD, risk assessment calculator²⁸ on at-risk population,
- Preliminary correlation analysis between the digital risk score and the dopaminergic deficiency, as measured by the DaTscan striatal binding ratio (SBR), in people with PD and healthy controls,
- Classifying three available cases of phenoconverters to evaluate the digital risk score prognostic value.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Dataset description

All data utilised in this analysis was sourced from the PPMI dataset. For a detailed description of the PPMI dataset refer to the section 3.1 of this document. Our analysis incorporated data from the Verily substudy of PPMI, during which the Verily Study Watch was utilized to collect data from a total of 357 participants. These comprised 161 individuals diagnosed with PD, 35 healthy controls, and 158 individuals at risk of developing PD. Participants from the SWEDD cohort and 1 PD participant who was excluded from the PPMI were not considered for the analysis. Participants were monitored using the Verily Study Watch for an average duration of 465.5 (\pm 213) days. During data collection, signals were captured using the smartwatch-embedded sensors, i.e., accelerometer, gyroscope, photoplethysmography, ambient temperature, ambient pressure, electrodermal activity, and humidity sensors.

To implement the MDS prodromal risk calculator, we sourced PD risk and prodromal markers according to the MDS task force criteria (Berg et al., 2015; Heinzl et al., 2019) from the general PPMI dataset, and the FOUND and ONLINE substudies.

Three cohorts are considered in this analysis as labelled by the PPMI:

1. Parkinson's disease
2. Healthy controls
3. Prodromal PD which are participants at-risk for developing PD.

For the purposes of PD risk estimation specific criteria were set for the participants to be eligible to enter the analysis pipeline. These are outlined below:

1. Participants are either diagnosed with PD or prodromal PD or are healthy controls
2. Participants are included in the Verily watch study subset.

²⁸ <https://www.movementdisorders.org/Prodromal-PD-Calculator.htm>

All available data, meeting the above inclusion criteria were used for developing the PD risk model. Hence, no sample size calculation was performed for the purpose of this model development.

6.2.2 Data pre-processing

Pre-calculated digital features

The PPMI dataset contains readily available pre-calculated feature time series that were derived during the Verily study and used as inputs to train the PD risk model. These pre-calculated features are categorized into three primary categories related to sleep, walking steps, and ambulatory activities. Each feature represents a time series derived from the raw data (**Table 6.1**). Algorithms used to derive those features are known, but models were not published as a result of lacking reproducibility. Any “NaN” (not-a-number) values present in the data were removed.

Table 6.1 Description of the pre-calculated Verily features available in the PPMI used in the PD risk prediction model

Metric Category	Feature	Description	Interval
Sleep	Total sleep time	Duration of sleep measured in minutes.	Day
	Total wake time after sleep onset	Total wake time after initially falling asleep.	Day
	Sleep Efficiency	Ratio of total sleep time to time in bed.	Day
	Number of Awakenings	Count of awakenings during the sleep period.	Day
	Total NREM Time	Duration of non-REM sleep.	Day
	Total REM Time	Duration of REM sleep.	Day
	Total Deep NREM Time	Duration of deep NREM (slow wave) sleep.	Day
	Total Light NREM Time	Duration of light NREM sleep.	Day
Step	Hourly Step Count Sum	Aggregated hourly step count, indicating overall daily activity.	Hour
Ambulatory	Sum Walking Minutes	Aggregated daily walking time, reflecting mobility and stability.	Hour

Feature aggregation

The three metric categories are measured in different time resolutions. Sleep metrics are measured per day, while step, ambulatory metrics are measured per hour. Thus, a feature aggregation approach was necessary. For this reason, time series derived features were automatically extracted using the Tsfresh²⁹ Python package (**Figure 6.1**). Minimal feature

²⁹ <https://tsfresh.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

computation was used, and 100 features were calculated in total. For each time series in present **Table 6.1** the following features were calculated:

- **Sum:** The total aggregate for each metric within the period of observation (e.g., total steps or total sleep time).
- **Median:** to understand the central tendency without the influence of outliers, offering a stable indicator of typical behaviour.
- **Mean:** The average value over the period of observation
- **Length:** The number of recorded observations within the metric's time series, reflecting the duration or frequency of data collection.
- **Measures of variability:** Provide insights into the stability or fluctuations within each metric, indicating consistency or variable in behaviors behaviours.
 - **Standard Deviation**
 - **Variance**
- **Root Mean Square:** A robust indicator of the intensity of activities, especially useful for detecting high or low-intensity periods.
- **Measures of range:** Identification of the peak and low points within the series, (e.g., maximum wake periods or minimum activity during sleep).
 - **Maximum value**
 - **Minimum value**
 - **Absolute Maximum:** Reflects extreme values that could signify atypical or unusual behaviour, capturing peaks irrespective of direction (positive or negative).

Figure 6.1 Calculation of an aggregated feature vector using tsfresh package

MDS risk model input

To determine the risk score of the MDS PD risk model for each individual in the at-risk cohort, we extracted the risk and prodromal markers (Berg et al., 2015; Heinzl et al., 2019) from the PPMI, PPMI-FOUND, and PPMI-ONLINE datasets. All risk markers were available (**Table 6.2**), except substantia nigra hyperechogenicity and DaT-scans (data access approval pending). Any variable collected later than the commencement of the Verily study was also excluded, except caffeine consumption and occupational pesticide exposure, as these are considered historical information.

We searched records of diagnoses in the Medical Conditions Log using regular expressions and marked pre-study diagnoses related to the MDS task force criteria as positive. Further, MDS-UPDRS scores of each visit, before the initiation of the Verily study, were evaluated and items exceeding predetermined thresholds were included. For PSG proven RBD, only the positive cases were considered, and missing information was marked as null.

PRS was also calculated and included as risk marker in the model. For details on PRS calculation refer to section 5 Genetic profiling for PD risk assessment and prognosis.

Variables unavailable for a participant were marked as null. No further handling of missing values was performed as the model is capable of handle missing values by ignoring them.

Table 6.2 MDS PD risk and prodromal markers

Variable	Source	Details
Age	PPMI	Mean age during the Verily Study
Biological sex	PPMI	-
Never smoked	FOUND	Answered No to the “Have you ever smoked regularly?”
Current smoker	FOUND	Answered Yes to the “Are you a current smoker question”
Former smoker	FOUND	Answered Yes to the “Have you ever smoked regularly?” and No to “Are you a current smoker question”
Caffeine consumption	FOUND, ONLINE	Answered Yes to the “Have you ever drank caffeinated coffee regularly?”
Occupational Pesticide exposure	FOUND, ONLINE	Answered Yes if they had a job that exposed them to pesticides
Polygenic risk score	CING	High or Low percentile of AMP-PD PRS
GBA Present	PPMI	From Participant Status
LRRK2 Present	PPMI	From Participant Status
1 st degree relative diagnosed with PD	PPMI	From Family History
Diabetes mellitus (Type II)	PPMI	Medication Log Records containing 'diabetes' (case insensitive) AND ('II' OR '2' OR 'mellitus'), excluding entries with 'pre' or 'border'
Polysomnography-confirmed REM sleep disorder	PPMI	In RBD prodromal sub-cohort
RBD screening questionnaire	PPMI	RBDSQ > 5
Sub-threshold parkinsonism	PPMI	MDS-UPDRS Part III score >6 Excluding postural and kinetic tremor
Diminished olfactory function	PPMI	In Hyposmia prodromal sub-cohort
Constipation	PPMI	Medication Log Records containing 'consti' (case insensitive)

		OR MDS-UPDRS Part I 1.11 > 1
Daytime somnolence	PPMI	Records containing 'sleepiness' (case insensitive) OR MDS-UPDRS Part I 1.8 > 1
Urinary dysfunction	PPMI	Records containing 'urin' (case insensitive) AND either 'incontinence', 'frequency', or 'urgency' OR MDS-UPDRS Part I 1.10 > 1
Orthostatic hypotension	PPMI	Records containing either 'headed' OR 'hypotension' OR MDS-UPDRS Part I 1.12 > 1
Neurogenic orthostatic hypotension	PPMI	At least one visit with orthostatic hypotension based on measurements and $\Delta HR/\Delta SBP < 0.5$ (Norcliffe-Kaufmann et al., 2018) as in the PPMI study of (Beach & McKay, 2024)
Erectile dysfunction	PPMI	Based on SCOPA-AUT question 22 OR Records containing either 'sexual' or 'erectile' (case insensitive)
Presence of clinical depression or depressive indicators	PPMI	Records containing the term 'depress' (case insensitive) OR MDS-UPDRS Part I 1.3 > 1
Cognitive function	PPMI	"Records containing the term 'cognitive' or variations (any case)" OR MDS-UPDRS Part I 1.1 > 1

New digital features

In the final version of the PD risk model, new digital features will be calculated to address the reproducibility limitations of the pre-calculated digital features provided by the Verily Study. These features are not yet included in the analysis, as the extraction pipelines are expected to complete processing by January 2025.

At the moment, we have developed our own feature extraction pipelines that are based on open-source algorithms. These pipelines were deployed on the raw smartwatch sensor data from the Verily Study downloaded from the PPMI after obtaining the relevant permission. The original data size of the raw sensor data comprised 70 TB stored in protocol buffer format³⁰. By implementing custom Python scripts to accelerate the process, we reduced the data size without any losses to approximately 12TB by converting existing data to Parquet³¹ format.

The selection of novel features was performed based on the importance of features present in other databases and those critical on measuring symptoms, such as slowness of movement

³⁰ <https://protobuf.dev/>

³¹ <https://parquet.apache.org/>

(Deliverable 3.1). **Table 6.3** contains an overview of the novel features that will be extracted along with the algorithm's source.

Table 6.3 Description of novel features extracted for PD risk prediction model based on Verily study raw sensor data

Feature category	Description	Algorithm
Signal Processing	Features describing the raw signal of the sensor.	Custom Python script
Sleep	Features based on sleep, such as duration, efficiency, REM minutes, etc	asleep ³²
Step	Features describing gait and walking, such as mins walking /day, steps/min	stepcount ³³
Physical activity	Activity level extracted by a human activity recognition model	Custom model trained on Capture24 ³⁴

6.2.3 Prediction models

In this analysis, we present a PD digital risk score estimation model that is based on digital measurements, demographics and somatometrics. The feature selection was based on data availability and their association to PD based on the current literature.

The digital risk model outputs the digital risk score which is the probability of being classified as PD. The probability threshold for a person to be classified as PD was optimized with ROC analysis by maximising Youden's Index. The digital risk score is then evaluated against the output probability of the MDS PD risk calculator³⁵. The MDS PD risk calculator is a naïve Bayesian classifier that assigns a pretest probability based on age which is adjusted with the presence of the MDS risk and prodromal markers. The calculator assigns in the prodromal stage if their risk probability exceeds 0.8. Further, the digital model was correlated with the Striatal Binding Ratio (SBR) from DaTscans of people with PD and healthy controls to evaluate the use of the digital score as a proxy for dopaminergic deficiency.

Feature selection was initially based on 3 distinct sources:

- a) an extensive state-of-the-art (SoA) review (outlined in detail in deliverable *D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets*),
- b) a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (KCL, FIN, CHUT, TUD) and
- c) data availability in the PPMI portal (IDA-LONI).

6.2.4 Analytical methods

The model was trained using 100 features calculated using the tsfresh library (Section 6.2.2), along with the mean age during the Verily Study, sex, height, and weight.

The dataset used in model training and evaluation included 153 PD and 34 healthy control participants. To mitigate the class imbalance, we used a Balanced Random Forest Classifier (BRFC) with 150 estimators. The model was trained and evaluated using a Leave-One-

³² <https://github.com/OxWearables/asleep>

³³ <https://github.com/OxWearables/stepcount>

³⁴ <https://github.com/OxWearables/capture24>

³⁵ <https://www.movementdisorders.org/Prodromal-PD-Calculator.htm>

Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation scheme. Standard scaling (z-score normalisation) was applied to each feature during training for each fold. To assess performance we utilised accuracy, precision, sensitivity, and specificity and f1-score. Furthermore, Receiver Operator Curve (ROC) and Precision-Recall Curve (PRC) analysis were conducted.

To explain model outcomes the GINI index-based feature importance was calculated by training the model on the entire dataset, and we extracted the SHAP values for each participant left out during the LOSO cross-validation scheme.

The ability of the model to predict dopaminergic deficiency was preliminarily investigated by correlating the digital risk score with the minimum SBR of left and right putamen of the DaTscan of the PD and healthy controls. As an extra clinical validation step, the digital risk score was correlated with the MDS PD risk score calculator outcomes.

The final model evaluation step was implemented by identifying identified 3 phenoconverters in the at-risk cohort who received a PD diagnosis after the end of the Verily study. The progression of the PD risk score throughout the Verily study was calculated. The cumulative risk scores for each participant were calculated for each month in the study.

6.2.5 Training versus evaluation

Our aim is to validate our results using abnormal DaTscan examination of the at-risk cohort as ground truth. However, due to our pending data access request for the DaTscan results of the at-risk population (PD prodromal cohort), the evaluation was limited to the PD and healthy control cohorts.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Participants

338 PPMI participants were considered for this analysis. The demographics and somatometrics of the participants fulfilling the inclusion criteria for this analysis are presented in **Table 6.4**. Nine participants from the Prodromal cohort have been identified by the PPMI consensus committee to have been diagnosed with PD. Therefore, they have been excluded from training.

Table 6.4 PD risk dataset description

	Parkinson's Disease	Healthy Controls	Prodromal
N	153	34	151
Male (%)	91 (59.48%)	20 (58.82%)	56 (37.09%)
Age at study initiation (std)	68.72 ± 8.08	66.96 ± 12.38	65.09 ± 7.11
Age distribution (N)			
<50 (%)	3 (1.96)	4 (11.76)	1 (0.66)
50-54 (%)	3 (1.96)	1 (2.94)	9 (5.96)
55-59 (%)	14 (9.15)	2 (5.88)	27 (17.88)
60-64 (%)	23 (15.03)	4 (11.76)	30 (19.87)
65-69 (%)	33 (21.57)	89(26.47)	44 (29.14)
70-74 (%)	39 (25.49)	5 (14.71)	31 (20.53)
75-79 (%)	28 (18.30)	3 (8.82)	7 (4.64)

>80 (%)	10 (6.54)	6 (17.65)	2 (1.32)
Weight in kg (std)	79.89 (19.04)	78.68 (18.36)	77.74 (18.38)
Height in cm (std)	169.65 (10.29)	170.76 (11.46)	167.21 (9.93)
Disease onset (std)	6.11 (2.44)		
MDS-UPDRS Part III (std)	29.41 (13.03)	2.97(2.83)	3.7 (6.16)

6.3.2 Model development

For this analysis, PD (n=153) and healthy controls (n=34) participants were used. All participants were used in training and validating the model by leveraging the LOSO cross-validation approach. The presence of PD diagnosis was used as the outcome. The results were correlated with the MDS PD Risk model. Further model updating, including hyperparameter tuning on the training set and evaluation of the at-risk population, will be performed once we access the DaT-scan results from the PPMI.

6.3.3 Model specification

The source code for this analysis was developed using Python 3.12. The scikit-learn³⁶ and imblearn³⁷ libraries were used for the models, seaborn³⁸ and matplotlib³⁹ for data visualization and scipy⁴⁰ for statistical testing. The analysis was performed on a workstation with the following specifications: (CPU: 24 core, 3.8GHz, RAM: 128GB, VRAM: 48GB). Upon completion of the analysis, the results will be published along with the developed source code after removing any identifying information of the dataset used.

6.3.4 Model performance

Our model demonstrated a good to excellent accuracy on the classification of PD vs healthy controls, as seen by results on **Table 6.5**. In addition, **Figure 6.2** illustrates the ROC and PRC curves for the model. The PRC is presented due to the presence of a class imbalance in the dataset that could potentially bias the AUC towards the outcome (PD diagnosis). Additionally, **Figure 6.3** depicts the distributions of the PD risk digital score predicted by our model for the three cohorts of the PPMI dataset, denoting significantly higher digital scores for people with PD compared to HC and prodromal participants. Noteworthy, the digital scores for the PD and healthy controls were calculated during the cross-validation, while the Prodromal cohort was calculated after training the model on the entire training set (PD and healthy controls).

Table 6.5 Performance of each model version in estimating PD risk. Demographics refer to Sex & Age and somatometrics include Height & Weight

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	Specificity	F1 Score	ROC AUC	PR AUC
Digital features & demographics & somatometrics	0.81	0.95	0.81	0.79	0.87	0.86	0.96

³⁶ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

³⁷ <https://imbalanced-learn.org/stable/>

³⁸ <https://seaborn.pydata.org>

³⁹ <https://matplotlib.org/stable/>

⁴⁰ <https://scipy.org>

Figure 6.2 ROC curve and PRC of the model informed by digital measurements, demographics and somatometrics.

Figure 6.3 Digital risk score grouped by PPMI cohort (PD, Healthy controls and Prodromal). Box plot centre line ≡ median; box limits ≡ upper and lower quartiles; whiskers ≡ 1.5 × IQR; dots ≡ individual predictions; **** $p \leq 1.00e-04$, ns not significant.

Figure 6.4 Balanced random forest GINI index-based feature importance of the top 10 features of the PD risk estimation model-based

Feature importance and model explainability

We calculated the GINI index-based feature importance by training the model on the entire training set (**Figure 6.4**). Sleep features predominate over the other categories (digital measurements, demographics, and somatometrics). SHAP analysis (**Figure 6.5**) confirmed this result, denoting that features associated to sleep were important in classifying between PD and HC. The discriminatory ability of the features is apparent as the distribution of the SHAP values for the two classes exhibit opposite skewness patterns. **Figure 6.6** presents the overall top 20 most important features based on their SHAP values and their influence on the model's classification of a participant as PD.

Figure 6.5 SHAP values distribution for classes PD vs Healthy controls for digital measurement only model

Figure 6.6 SHAP values for the top 20 features for the digital measurements only model.

Model calibration and uncertainty quantification

Model calibration ensures that the probability predicted corresponds to the probable occurrence rate. **Figure 6.7** depicts the reliability curve of our model. It is evident that the model overestimates the probability of the outcome (class PD). In addition, for a binary classifier, the reliability curve can be seen as a measure of uncertainty as its inherent over/underestimation for a certain probability is known before the inference.

To alleviate the probability overestimation of the model we performed a model calibration using a meta-estimator with `CalibratedClassifierCV` (scikit-learn) with sigmoid method.

Figure 6.7 Reliability curves of the uncalibrated and calibrated PD risk estimation model

Correlation with the Striatal Binding Ratio

To preliminary examine the capability of the model to predict the dopaminergic deficiency, we correlated the digital score from our models with the DaTscan results from PD and healthy populations. Due to the progressive nature of PD, DaTscan of PD patients that were undertaken 3 years before the Verily study were excluded. With this constraint, data were available for $n=93$ PD and $n=34$ Healthy controls. As an SBR value, we used the minimum value from the left and right putamen from the DaT-scan closest to the Verily study initiation for each participant. To calculate the correlation, we performed a LOSO training scheme on the subset with DaT-scan availability for the digital measurement, demographics, and somatometrics. The model outputs were correlated with the SBR. A moderate negative correlation was observed from the analysis (**Figure 6.8**). This correlation is mainly driven by the apparent difference in dopaminergic deficiency between the PD and HC groups, which further highlights the model's potential diagnostic value.

Figure 6.8 Correlation between the digital score for PD and healthy control population and the minimum putamen SBR

Correlation with the MDS risk model

To compare how well our model’s digital risk score aligns with the MDS PD risk model, we predicted the digital risk scores for the at-risk population. Subsequently, we calculated the PD risk as given by the MDS PD risk model, and the two scores were correlated. A moderate correlation was observed (**Figure 6.9**).

Figure 6.9 Correlation between the digital risk score and the MDS PD risk model derived score

Digital risk score ad-hoc analysis for the phenoconverters

To further validate the diagnostic utility of the model, three individuals were identified from the at-risk cohort who received a PD diagnosis up to 3 years after the end of Verily Study. An *ad-hoc* analysis was conducted to provisionally investigate if the digital risk score can detect possible progression of PD. The digital score was calculated for each individual across

months, starting from month 1 and progressively incorporating data from subsequent months (e.g., up to month 2, month 4, etc). This cumulative approach allows for the detection of temporal trends and variations in the Digital Score as data accumulates over time. By analysing how features evolve with the inclusion of each new month's data, we aimed to identify significant patterns and shifts, providing insights into longitudinal changes in the underlying digital behaviours.

The digital risk score predicted based on the cumulative aggregation of all the available data points during the entire observation period, yielded the following probabilities for each prodromal subject: 0.82 for Prodromal_1, 0.73 for Prodromal_2, and 0.85 for Prodromal_3. **Figure 6.10** illustrates the trajectories of the digital score for the identified phenoconverters from the at-risk group (n=3) and the healthy controls (n=7) with similar mean ages (70.93 vs. 70.67, $p = 0.92$).

The SHAP waterfall plots (**Figure 6.11**) of the digital risk mode confirmed the importance of the sleep patterns and walking in the final decision of the model for the three phenoconverters.

Figure 6.10 Digital risk score trajectories for the 3 phenoconverters and 8 age-matched healthy controls

For Total REM Time Median, the boxplot (**Figure 6.12**) reveals that prodromal individuals exhibit intermediate REM sleep durations between healthy controls and PD participants, supporting the model's reliance on this feature for accurate predictions. Similarly, prodromal subjects show reduced walking activity compared to healthy controls, as evidenced by the sum walking minutes median, reflecting an early decrease in physical activity as a predictor of PD conversion. The feature Sleep Efficiency Mean highlights a clear gradient, where prodromal individuals display lower sleep efficiency than healthy controls but higher than PD patients.

Figure 6.11 SHAP values of the PD risk score model for the phenoconverters

Figure 6.12 Feature distribution of the phenoconverters compared to PD and healthy controls

6.4 Discussion

6.4.1 Interpretation

The results of the present experiment demonstrate the good to excellent diagnostic accuracy of the wearable data to estimate the risk to develop PD. This is evidenced based on five distinct findings:

- The high model performance metrics when classifying PD from HC
- The good correlation coefficient when the digital score was correlated against the SBR.
- The fair to good correlation coefficient when the digital score was correlated against MDS-risk score
- The model correctly predicted the conversion to PD for 3 participants, for whom the digital data capture preceded PD diagnosis.

The lower correlation between the digital score and the MDS risk model could be explained by the multiple clinical markers in the MDS model (such as diabetes or orthostatic hypotension diagnosis) that features used in analysis fail to capture. Further, the MDS risk model is based on subjective examinations, which may render it imperfect in accurately estimating the true risk of developing PD.

The results of this study pave the way for the updating of the PD risk model. The models developed will eventually be evaluated on an at-risk population (Prodromal Cohort) with the outcome being the presence of abnormal DaT-scan, which can identify striatal dopaminergic neuron loss in the substantia nigra. Consequently, the striatal dopaminergic deficiency will be used as a proxy for the risk of developing PD, making this approach fully aligned with the AI-PRA study and enabling models to be further evaluated using prospective data.

6.4.2 Limitations

- A key limitation in developing PD risk estimation models is the scarcity of datasets containing both longitudinal data and wrist-based digital measurements from individuals prior to their PD diagnosis. To overcome the lack of data from people that obtained a confirmed PD diagnosis, we intend to utilise striatal dopaminergic deficiency as a proxy for the risk of developing PD. This approach is fully aligned with the AI-PRA study procedures. As of the time of writing this deliverable, our access request to the DaTscans and UPSIT for the at-risk (Prodromal) cohort of the PPMI is pending.
- The MDS PD risk and prodromal criteria likelihood ratios are based on multiple large cohort studies. As a result, their inclusion to increase model robustness is a challenge due to the small sample size of the training set.
- The correlation of the digital score with the SBR of the PD and healthy controls can be considered only as preliminary research and validation of our fundamental hypothesis that dopaminergic deficiency may be utilised as a method of PD risk prediction. The true utility of such a model can only be validated using data from the at-risk population. PD participants exhibit obvious dopaminergic deficiency while healthy controls do not, thus the model functions as a classifier. With the use of prodromal PD participants in the evaluation we can test the inferential capability of the model to interpolate a digital score closely corresponds to the dopaminergic deficiency level.
- Further, digital measurement data in this analysis are limited to the pre-calculated features derived from the Verily Study.

6.4.3 Next steps and future directions

Mitigation approaches are to be implemented in the next (updated) model version (*D3.4 – Final report on predictive modelling for PD*).

- Model validation using DaTscans and a-Synuclein Seed Amplification Assay (SAA). This PPMI Tier 3 data are expected to be accessed in January 2025.

- MDS PD risk and prodromal markers will be inferred from the analysed digital measurements, such as physical activity and presence of RBD. These biomarkers have already been developed and reported in *D3.1 First report on digital biomarkers for PD*
- MDS PD risk and prodromal criteria will be added as inputs to the models to assess their prognostic value on the top of the already developed PD risk models presented in this deliverable.
- While we have obtained access to Tier 3 raw signal data, its size (70 TB) has hindered our progress. Nevertheless, we have managed to perform data engineering by restructuring it more efficiently on the disk, reducing the size to 12 TB. Currently, feature extraction algorithms are being developed and implemented to analyse the data and derive a broad array of features.
- The overall hope is that both healthcare professionals and clinical researchers will use the model to make more informed decisions about the management of the disease. This utility is to be tested during the AI-PRA study

7 Development and evaluation of a model to predict PD progression

7.1 Background and objectives

PD is a neurodegenerative progressive disorder, presenting significant advancements in both motor and non-motor impairments. Clinically, the ability to predict the progression of PD is very important for clinicians and patients alike, since the early identification of transitions in motor function decline marks a significant turn in treatment pathways and improves the quality of life. The rationale behind developing a PD progression model comes from the shortcomings of diagnostic tools and the fact that the available models often cannot consider variable courses that individual patients take. Most existing models focus on short-term predictions, but there remains a significant gap in long-term, individualized prognostic models that can assist in tailoring treatment over time.

The target population is patients diagnosed with PD, especially during the early to mid-stage of the disease, who could benefit from timely adjustment in treatment plans based on forecasted changes in motor function and disability levels. This predictive model will serve personalized care within the PD care pathway by accurately predicting disease progression. Specifically, the progression score that the model targets is the total score of the MDS-UPDRS Part 3, which focuses on motor symptoms commonly affected by PD. As a first step, we are developing a model that integrates baseline features, such as demographic and clinical characteristics, along with data collected from follow-up visits, to predict the MDS-UPDRS part 3 (motor) score 12 months into the future. Ultimately, the PD progression predictive model will be used by healthcare professionals to individualize disease management and by patients who will be looped in their disease monitoring procedure. The incorporation into MAI-care for patient engagement and MAI-insights for clinical oversight ensures functionality for both the patient and the provider with data-driven tools.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Dataset description

We initiated our PD progression modelling by incorporating data from the PPMI dataset, which is sourced from a comprehensive longitudinal observational study. Follow-up periods, which are important for the PD progression model, vary depending on the cohort, with some participants monitored for up to five years or longer, enabling robust tracking of disease progression over time.

For this analysis, we included only participants with a confirmed PD diagnosis at baseline who also met specific criteria for consistent follow-up. These participants underwent regular clinical assessments, motor and non-motor symptom evaluations, and biomarker collection, providing a robust longitudinal data series crucial for tracking disease progression over time. Our inclusion criteria thus centered on those participants who had been monitored for a minimum of 12 months, enabling reliable modelling of progressive symptom changes and disease markers.

7.2.2 Data pre-processing

This section outlines the comprehensive data preprocessing steps performed on the PPMI dataset. The preprocessing involved loading multiple datasets, merging data sources, encoding categorical variables, and handling missing values to prepare a clean dataset for analysis.

7.2.2.1 Handling Missing Values

The PPMI dataset is missing considerable values, between these visits especially. In particular, this holds for the target variable MDS-UPDRS part 3, which is the total MDS-UPDRS part 3 score. **Table 7.1** shows the percentage of missing values from the baseline (BL) to visit 20 (V20), corresponding to about 156 months after the baseline data collection. The missing value problem is not limited to only MDS-UPDRS part 3 but is common in other clinical features for the PPMI dataset as well. For instance, there are a few missing values for MDS-UPDRS part 3 at baseline, accounting for only 7.15%. However, this number increases steadily per visit until it reaches as high as 99.74% at visit 20. So as to mitigate the effect of these missing values on our data, we have implemented imputation strategies, when possible, for specific variables like the state (PDSTATE; on or off medication) and sex (SEX), which were essential for the analysis. Additionally, complete case analysis was conducted for features where imputation was not feasible or practical, ensuring that the dataset remained as comprehensive and reliable as possible for future modelling.

Table 7.1 Percentage of missing values for MDS-UPDRS PART3 across visits in the PPMI dataset

Timestamp	Time average (SD) (Months)	Missing value % (MDS-UPDRS part 3)
BL	0	7,153285
V01	3.26 (0.75)	84,992701
V02	6.44 (1.12)	56,875912
V03	9.30 (0.83)	86,773723
V04	12.67 (1.38)	47,824818
V05	18.42 (1.20)	65,343066

V06	24.62 (1.50)	62,59854
V07	30.32 (0.96)	77,051095
V08	36.62 (1.65)	70,218978
V09	42.23 (0.88)	81,751825
V10	48.83 (1.85)	72,262774
V11	54.30 (1.10)	86,686131
V12	60.79 (1.99)	74,832117
V13	72.80 (1.95)	83,737226
V14	84.59 (1.65)	84,934307
V15	96.97 (2.43)	90,510949
V16	109.12 (2.02)	93,89781
V17	120.74 (2.02)	93,255474
V18	132.91 (1.74)	95,153285
V19	144.70 (1.43)	97,664234
V20	156.21 (1.10)	99,737226

7.2.2.2 Imputing PDSTATE

The PDSTATE variable had a significant percentage of missing values, which could impact the analysis. To resolve this, we utilized two key variables—PAG_NAME and PDTRTMNT—to infer the missing PDSTATE values. Specifically:

- If PAG_NAME equaled 'NUPDRS3OF', PDSTATE was set to 'OFF' (coded as 0).
- If PAG_NAME equaled 'NUPDRS3ON', PDSTATE was set to 'ON' (coded as 1).
- If PDTRTMNT indicated no treatment (0), PDSTATE was set to 'OFF'. This process involved mapping the string labels of PAG_NAME and PDSTATE into numerical codes (OFF as 0, ON as 1) and applying the rules to impute the missing values, which resulted in a substantial reduction of missing PDSTATE entries.

7.2.2.3 Imputing SEX

The SEX variable also exhibited a high percentage of missing values in the demographic data. To infer these values, we used sex-specific responses from the SCOPA-AUT questionnaire, mapping the responses to infer the sex of participants:

- Responses to female-specific questions (items 22, 23, 23a) were coded as 0 (female).
- Responses to male-specific questions (items 24,25) were coded as 1 (male)

By analysing SCOPA-AUT items, we were able to assign a new feature to infer the missing SEX values, further improving the dataset's completeness.

7.2.2.4 Complete Case Analysis

After implementing the imputation strategies, we conducted a complete case analysis to ensure the remaining dataset was fully complete. This involved removing any rows with

remaining missing values. The aim is to simplify the subsequent analyses by ensuring a complete dataset, avoiding the complexity and potential biases of more extensive imputation

7.2.3 Prediction models

Due to the structure of the PPMI database, which consists of multiple CSV files, each containing different types of patient information such as demographics, clinical data, and imaging results, we performed feature selection across various PPMI datasets. Feature inclusion was based on 3 distinct sources:

- a) an extensive state-of-the-art (SoA) review (please refer to deliverable *D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets*),
- b) a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (KCL, FIN, CHUT, TUD) to ensure that the model is clinically informed by expert opinions and
- c) data availability in the PPMI portal (IDA-LONI).

The AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners identified a total of 297 indicators, with the majority sourced from motor assessments (**Table 7.2**). As a first step in the development process, we selected a subset of features from the identified indicators. Subsequently, further selection was based on two key criteria: the availability of data, measured by the percentage of missing values for each feature, and the redundancy of these features as determined through a thorough literature review. In another approach, we utilized the entire set of identified indicators, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of the data. We retained only those features where missing values did not exceed a prespecified threshold of 10%. This preprocessing step resulted in a reduced but robust set of 165 predictors.

Table 7.2 Summary of indicators identified from the PPMI dataset for PD progression model development

Category	Number of indicators
Subject Characteristics	16
Biospecimen	2
Imaging	10
Medical History	69
Motor Assessments	165
Non-motor Assessments	35
Total	297

7.2.3.1 Engineering new features to enhance data richness

Since some indicators are not found directly in the PPMI datasets, several new features were engineered due to their strong relation to PD progression.

- **Genetic Mutation Classification:**

A new feature “Genetic Mutation Status” was computed to classify participants based on their genetic profiles. It is a binary feature and reports whether a participant has a genetic mutation in PD associated genes such as *LRRK2*, *GBA*, *SNCA*, *PRKN*, and *PINK1*. Value “1” is used for the presence of a mutation in any of the related genes and “0” for the absence of a mutation in these genes.

- **Disease Duration Calculation:** Calculated as the difference between participant's enrolment date and date of PD diagnosis.
- **Composite Scores from Questionnaires:** Several new composite scores were generated by summing items from various questionnaires used in the PPMI dataset:
 - **SCOPA-AUT Total Score:** This score sums all autonomic function items.
 - **QUIP Total Score:** A total score was generated from selected items related to impulse control disorders.
 - **Geriatric Depression Scale Score:** This score was calculated by summing responses to the Geriatric Depression Scale, with adjustments for reverse-scored items.
 - **Epworth Sleepiness Scale Score:** This composite score summed all sleepiness-related items.
 - **REM Sleep Behavior Disorder Score:** In this questionnaire, there are primary questions focused on specific symptoms and behaviours associated with RBD, such as experiencing vivid dreams and engaging in potentially injurious activities during sleep. The final question addresses the presence of neurological conditions, such as Parkinsonism, epilepsy, and stroke. In the PPMI dataset, to calculate the total RBD score, a subset of columns representing these primary questions are selected. These columns are then summed across each row (for each participant) to produce an initial score. For the final question on neurological conditions, each condition has its own column in the PPMI dataset. Therefore, we used the maximum value across these columns to represent the presence of any relevant condition. This maximum function captures the presence of any condition that could contribute to RBD, rather than summing all conditions, which avoids overestimating the impact of multiple conditions.

7.2.3.2 Features subset and outcome definition

The development of our initial model focused on a selected subset of the identified relevant features commonly found in existing literature (see **Table 7.3**). In this deliverable, we concentrated on this subset to develop our first model, with the ultimate aim of incorporating additional features in future model updates. The selection of this subset is based on its relevance to PD progression, which is also apparent in previously published research. The features were obtained from baseline data, as well as from Visit 02 and Visit 04 (approximately 6 months and 12 months after baseline respectively).

Table 7.3 Summary of the selected features and their definitions

Feature	Description
ENROLL_AGE	The age of the participant at the time of enrolment.
gen_mutation	A binary feature indicating whether the participant has a genetic mutation linked to PD.
MDS-UPDRS PART 3	Total score from the MDS-UPDRS Part 3, assessing motor function.
PDSTATE	A feature indicating whether the participant is in the "ON" or "OFF" medication state.
NHY	Hoehn and Yahr stage, a commonly used scale to measure PD progression.
DiseaseDuration_Years	The duration of the participant's disease, calculated from diagnosis to the visit date.
NP1RTOT	Total score from MDS-UPDRS Part 1, assessing non-motor experiences of daily living.
NP2PTOT	Total score from MDS-UPDRS Part 2, assessing motor experiences of daily living.
MCATOT	Montreal cognitive assessment total score, measuring cognitive function.
Total_SCOPA_Score	The sum of items assessing autonomic dysfunction (SCOPA-AUT).

Sex_scopa	Imputed sex based on responses to sex-specific SCOPA-AUT questions.
Total QUIP_Score	Total score from the Questionnaire for Impulsive-Compulsive Disorders in Parkinson's Disease (QUIP).
GDS_SCORE	Total score from the geriatric depression scale.
ESS_Score	Total score from the Epworth sleepiness scale.
MSEADLG	Modified Schwab and England activities of daily living score

The primary outcome of the model is the total MDS-UPDRS part 3 at Visit 04 which is 12 months after baseline, focusing on motor examination. This score captures the severity of motor symptoms such as tremor, bradykinesia, and rigidity, walking deteriorations and postural imbalance, which are central to PD progression. MDS-UPDRS part 3 is widely recognized in clinical settings as a gold-standard tool for evaluating motor impairment in PD, ensuring that the outcome is both clinically significant and familiar to healthcare providers. The choice of V04 (12 months) allows for an evaluation of short-term progression, providing insights into how the disease evolves within a critical time frame where treatment adjustments are often considered.

7.2.4 Analytical methods

At this stage of our model development, two modelling approaches were utilized, Neural Network regression model, and a Random Forest regression model.

The Neural Network regression model is implemented using TensorFlow⁴¹ and Keras⁴². This architecture was chosen because the neural networks can effectively deal with complex nonlinear relationships, intrinsic in clinical data, which are useful for modelling the intricate dependencies present in the progression of PD. We applied some regularization techniques, (1) *Batch Normalization after each dense layer*: we used batch normalization to stabilize the learning and reduce internal covariate shifts; this speeds up model convergence. (2) *Dropout layers, after each batch normalization layer*: the dropout rate was maintained at 0.3. This technique was used to prevent overfitting by randomly dropping units in training so that the network does not get dependent on a specific feature. For model compilation, Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 has been used for model training. Adam is particularly suitable for problems with large sets of data and sparse gradients. Since MSE was chosen as the loss function, which is suitable for regression tasks in which minimizing the squared differences between predicted and actual values is desired. Besides, MAE was tracked during training to provide extra insight into the model's performance by tracking the average of absolute errors. Moreover, to verify the generalization of the model for different data subsets, a 5-fold cross-validation was performed. The purpose of this technique was to help counter overfitting problems and provide a more realistic approximation for the performance of this model. In addition, early stopping is implemented, stopping the training once the validation loss did not improve within 10 epochs. Further, the best weights are restored based on validation loss to guarantee optimal performance.

In addition, other performance metrics were calculated to the model with best weights:

- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): The square root of MSE, which provides the error in the same units as the target variable.

⁴¹ <https://www.tensorflow.org>

⁴² <https://keras.io>

- R-squared (R^2): This statistic indicates the proportion of variance in the target variable (MDS-UPDRS PART 3) explained by the model, providing a measure of model fit.

Secondly, a Random Forest Regressor was utilized, which is an ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees to enhance prediction accuracy. During the 5-fold cross-validation process, the Random Forest model computed feature importances, allowing us to identify which predictors had the most influence on the decisions of the model when predicting the target variable, total MDS-UPDRS part 3.

7.2.5 Training versus evaluation

In the cross-validation described above, the test subjects are independent of both training and validation processes; hence, it ensures that the assessment of the model performance will not be biased. At this stage, we utilized only the PPMI dataset for both training and evaluation, though in the future steps of the project, we will use more datasets like NS-Park to test our model. This will test the generalizability of the model across cohorts and different clinical environments, thereby enhancing its robustness and applicability to other populations with PD.

During model training, we fine-tuned several hyperparameters to optimize performance. The final configuration used to achieve the presented results includes:

- Learning rate: 0.001
- Epochs: 200
- Batch size: 32
- Patience for early stopping: 10

These hyperparameters were adjusted iteratively to improve model performance while preventing overfitting and ensuring stable convergence during training.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Participants

For the PD progression model, the target population consists of PD patients. Extracted from the PPMI dataset, the data of a total of 1801 participants, all diagnosed with PD, were utilized. The participant analysis was conducted using BL data, as shown in the figures provided. The sex distribution of the participants shows that 62.5% were male and 37.5% were female (**Figure 7.1**), while the majority of participants identified as white (93.4%), with smaller percentages identifying as African American, Asian, Ashkenazi Jewish, and other racial groups (**Figure 7.2**).

Figure 7.1 Percentage of males (1) and females (0) in the PD cohort

Figure 7.2 Percentage of participants identifies as white (1) and other racial groups (0)

The average age at enrolment was 62.88 years, with a standard deviation of 9.72 years. While the average number of years of education was 15.96 years, indicating a well-educated population overall (refer to **Table 7.4**).

Table 7.4 Summary of Age at Enrolment, Age at Visit, and Years of Education Among PD Participants

Feature	Count	Mean	Std	Min	Max	Missing %
Age at Enrolment	1326	62.88	9.72	29.3	85.2	26.49
Age at Visit	1363	62.85	9.77	29.3	85.2	21.03
Number of Years of Education	1748	15.96	3.4	0	32	0.8

The primary outcome of interest is the total MDS-UPDRS part 3 score, which evaluates motor function severity in PD patients. **Figure 7.3** shows the distribution of total MDS-UPDRS part 3 scores across genetic subgroups, while **Figure 7.4** provides a comparison of total MDS-UPDRS part 3 scores across different age ranges. These figures highlight how genetic predisposition and age impact motor symptom severity. The sporadic group had a median/mean MDS-UPDRS PART 3 of 21/22.51, while the genetic group had 18/20.57. The difference was statistically significant by both an independent-samples t-test ($p=0.0074$) and a Mann-Whitney U test ($p=0.000052$). The total MDS-UPDRS part 3 medians tended to increase with age since the severity of motor symptoms in older PD patients is usually worse. As mentioned before, the study spans across multiple visits, but the analysis primarily focuses on BL, 6 months, and 12 months, which would enable us to understand the change in PD over a year.

Figure 7.3 Box Plot of MDS-UPDRS PART 3 scores by Genetic Subgroup

Figure 7.4 Box Plot of MDS-UPDRS PART 3 scores by Age Range

7.3.2 Model development

At this point, we have implemented three different approaches toward developing the PD progression model. In all approaches, the analysis included patients in the "OFF" medication state at all visits. This filtering ensures consistency in the motor state, as the "ON" state may introduce variability caused by the effects of medication rather than true disease progression.

- **Baseline Data Only:** In this first approach, only the baseline data were used. After preprocessing and handling missing data, 484 participants were included in the analysis. A total of 15 input features were used in this approach, which were extracted from the baseline data.
- **Baseline + Visit 02 Data:** This approach incorporated baseline and visit 02 (6 months after baseline) and hence yielded a smaller though more refined sample of 358 subjects, for which the features from visit 02 were used longitudinally to extend the capability of the model in making the predictions. A total of 22 features were used, including the 14 baseline features and the following 8 additional features from visit 02 (MDS-UPDRS PART 3 at v02, Hoehn and Yahr at v02, MDS-UPDRS part 1 at v02, MDS-UPDRS part 2 at v02, SCOPA score at v02, QUIP score at v02, ESS score at v02, Schwab and England v02).
- **All Indicators Approach:** In this approach, we utilized the complete set of available indicators identified by clinical partners, combining data from both baseline and visit 02. After preprocessing, features with more than 10% missing values were excluded, leaving 165 predictors from both visits in the analysis. This approach maximized the use of available data and explored the potential impact of a wider feature set.

The target outcome in all approaches is the total MDS-UPDRS part 3 score at visit 04. The model was trained and evaluated to predict time-dependent progression in motor symptoms in PD patients based on this outcome.

7.3.3 Model specification

As mentioned before, for the prediction model, two main modelling approaches are used: a Neural Network (NN) and a Random Forest. The model was implemented using TensorFlow and Keras for the neural network, and Scikit-learn for the random forest. The models were designed for regression tasks for predicting the MDS-UPDRS part 3 score at visit 04. The architecture of each model is summarised in **Table 7.5**.

Table 7.5 Summary of Neural Network and Random Forest model architectures for Predicting PD Progression.

Model	Component	Details
Neural Network	Input Layer	Accepts input features with shape matching the number of predictors.
	First Hidden Layer	- Neurons: 256
		- Activation: ReLU
		- Regularization: L2 ($\lambda = 0.01$)
		- Batch Normalization
	Second Hidden Layer	- Dropout: 0.3
		- Neurons: 128
		- Activation: ReLU
		- Regularization: L2 ($\lambda = 0.01$)
	Third Hidden Layer	- Batch Normalization
		- Dropout: 0.3
		- Neurons: 64
		- Activation: ReLU
Output Layer	- Regularization: L2 ($\lambda = 0.01$)	
	- Dropout: 0.3	
Optimizer	- Neurons: 1	
Loss Function	- Activation: Linear (for regression)	
Validation	Adam with learning rate = 0.001	
Random Forest	Input Features	Mean Squared Error (MSE)
	Number of Estimators	5-fold cross-validation
	Criterion	100
	Validation	Mean Squared Error (MSE)

7.3.4 Model performance

For the first two approaches (Baseline Only and Baseline + Visit 02), we used the data to train both the neural network model and the random forest model. In the third approach (All Indicators), we focused on training the RF model only. This decision was driven by two factors: first, the RF model is able to handle datasets where some missing values might remain, and second, the ability to extract feature importance values from the model to better understand the contribution of individual predictors in a comprehensive feature set. In **Figure 7.5** and **Figure 7.6**, we present the accuracy of the model predictions of MDS-UPDRS part 3 total score at visit 04 for baseline data and baseline data + V02, respectively. In addition, **Table 7.6** summarizes the performance of the neural network and random forest models for predicting the total MDS-UPDRS part 3 score (MDS-UPDRS part 3) at visit 04. The results shown are

the averages with standard deviations across each fold of the cross-validation procedure. In addition, the feature importance extracted from these random forests (as computed by the mean decrease in impurity) is illustrated in **Figure 7.7** and **Figure 7.8**.

Figure 7.5 Actual vs. predicted UPDRS total scores at visit 04 using BL data

Figure 7.6 Actual vs. predicted UPDRS total scores at visit 04 using BL + visit 02 data

Table 7.6 Model performance for predicting MDS-UPDRS part 3 (MDS-UPDRS PART 3) score at visit 04

Model	Input Features	MSE	RMSE	MAE	R ²	Pearson Correlation
Neural Network (BL)	Baseline Features Only (14)	58.02 ± 4.13	7.61 ± 0.27	6.02 ± 0.27	0.48 ± 0.08	0.72 ± 0.04
Random Forest (BL)	Baseline Features Only (14)	61.95 ± 4.06	7.87 ± 0.26	6.12 ± 0.32	0.45 ± 0.07	0.68 ± 0.07
Neural Network (BL+V02)	Baseline + Visit 02 Features (22)	50.04 ± 7.89	7.05 ± 0.55	5.66 ± 0.49	0.53 ± 0.11	0.76 ± 0.05
Random Forest (BL+V02)	Baseline + Visit 02 Features (22)	50.94 ± 6.39	7.12 ± 0.45	5.55 ± 0.48	0.53 ± 0.05	0.73 ± 0.05
Random Forest (All Indicators)	All BL and V02 Features (165)	53.16 ± 7.21	7.27 ± 0.48	5.55 ± 0.41	0.52 ± 0.08	0.73 ± 0.08

Figure 7.7 Feature importance for baseline features

Figure 7.8 Feature importance for baseline + visit 02 (BL+V02) features

Table 7.7 Top 10 Features in the All-Indicators Approach

Rank	Feature	Importance
1	MDS-UPDRS PART 3 _v02	0.31848
2	MDS-UPDRS PART 3 _bi	0.28295
3	NP2PTOT_v02	0.01401
4	DiseaseDuration_Years_bi	0.01292
5	MCATOT_bi	0.01084
6	NP3RIGRU_bi	0.00877
7	NP2PTOT_bi	0.00799
8	NP1PTOT_v02	0.00778
9	ENROLL_AGE_bi	0.00761
10	AGE_AT_VISIT_bi	0.00739

7.4 Discussion

7.4.1 Interpretation

The development of the PD progression model using three approaches—Baseline Data Only, Baseline + Visit 02, and “all Indicators”—has provided valuable insights into the prediction of motor progression. In all approaches, only patients in the “OFF” medication state at all visits were included to ensure consistency in the motor state.

In the Baseline Data Only approach, both NN and RF models demonstrated promising results, with the RF model showing slightly better performance. The error metrics for the RF model, such as MSE of 61.95 ± 4.06 and Pearson Correlation Coefficient of 0.68 ± 0.07 , suggest its robustness in capturing non-linear patterns in the data. The NN model also performed reasonably well, with an MSE of 58.02 ± 4.13 and a Pearson Correlation Coefficient of 0.72 ± 0.04 . Feature importance analysis in this approach highlighted baseline MDS-UPDRS part 3 and disease duration as the most informative predictors, aligning with clinical knowledge that motor symptom severity and time since diagnosis are critical in determining PD progression.

The Baseline + Visit 02 approach incorporated longitudinal data, which improved model performance. The RF model achieved an MSE of 50.94 ± 6.39 and a Pearson Correlation Coefficient of 0.73 ± 0.05 , while the NN model achieved an MSE of 50.04 ± 7.89 and a Pearson Correlation Coefficient of 0.76 ± 0.05 . These improvements underline the value of integrating data from multiple time points to capture dynamic changes in disease progression. Feature importance analysis for this approach revealed that MDS-UPDRS PART 3 from Visit 02 became the most predictive feature, reflecting the relevance of recent motor assessments in forecasting progression.

The “all Indicators” approach leveraged the full set of 165 features extracted from Baseline and Visit 02 data, utilizing only the RF model due to its capability to handle larger feature sets and tolerate some missing data. This approach achieved an MSE of 53.16 ± 7.21 and a Pearson Correlation Coefficient of 0.73 ± 0.08 , further highlighting the utility of incorporating comprehensive clinical indicators. Feature importance analysis in this approach confirmed the dominance of MDS-UPDRS PART 3 from Visit 02, baseline MDS-UPDRS PART 3, and disease duration, while also emphasizing contributions from additional motor and non-motor assessments, such as SCOPA-AUT and ESS scores.

7.4.2 Limitations

One limitation is that this work relies exclusively on the PPMI dataset, which, although robust and rich in features, is limited in diversity and scope compared to other datasets representing other populations and clinical settings. Current models have been trained and tested on this single dataset, and their generalizability to diverse clinical populations remains untested. This limitation raises questions about the generalizability of the models across different patient samples and treatment settings. The final version of the model will be validated on external datasets to ensure model generalizability.

Moreover, for consistency, the analysis is limited to patients in the “OFF” state of medication with the idea of reducing variability that may be introduced by the effects of medication. Although this strategy increases internal validity by focusing on the real course of the disease, it excludes a remarkable number of patients with PD whose ratings are given during the “ON” state. This limitation could be further improved in the future, possibly by deriving different models or additional features of medication changes. Alternatively, motor progression could

be predicted using other features besides the total UPDRS III score. For example, exploring the delta UPDRS III (change between visits) in the “ON” state

7.4.3 Usability of the model in the context of current care

This current work lays a foundation for iterative improvements. Future work shall thus focus on:

- **Wearable and Digital Biomarker Data:** The integration of wearable data has the potential to enrich the temporal resolution of this model. Such an integration would allow the detection of subtle changes in disease progression, which would enhance the predictive accuracy.
- **Fast and Slow Progressors/Regressors:** The classification of fast and slow progressors and regressors will enable fine-tuning predictive models to capture individual-specific progression trajectories with greater precision. The clinical implication of these subgroups in the future and their incorporation in the modeling approach will be further explored.
- **Exploring Advanced Modeling Techniques:** While the Random Forest model has proven robust, incorporating advanced approaches may enhance model performance and better capture the complexity of disease progression.
- **Real-world testing and evaluation in different clinical environments,** along with testing the model with different datasets, would be highly important for checking its generalizability. This will let one understand the performance level of the model across different types of patients and data collection protocols, and it is useful in fine-tuning and confirming the wider use of the model in the clinic.

8 Development and evaluation of a model to predict side effects related to PD medication

8.1 Background and objectives

While there is no cure for PD today, medications such as levodopa and dopamine agonists are commonly used to manage the symptoms. However, these medications and/or their mode of administration are associated with various side effects, including dyskinesias (i.e., involuntary movements), hallucinations, mood changes, excessive daytime sleepiness, and motor fluctuations. Over time, as the symptoms of PD exacerbate, maintaining the effectiveness of the medication may require higher dosages and increases the risk of these side effects occurring. In addition, the progressing disease severity might impact how the medication interacts with the subject and affect how and when side-effects occur.

The goal of this research is to investigate the effect of these medications through predictive modelling. If successful, this could allow for personalized treatment plans, adapting the medication dosage to patient-specific characteristics and circumstances. For instance, the minimum dosage that results in a certain primary outcome, while minimizing the risk of adverse effects could be predicted on a per-patient basis, providing a marked impact on quality of life. In what follows, our scope will be focused on dyskinesia's, but the developed frameworks will be equally applicable to other adverse effects later on.

8.2 Methods

8.2.1 Dataset description

All data used in this study (both for the development and the evaluation) were obtained from the CPP Integrated Parkinson's Database as described in Section 3.2. While the goal is to include as many of the datasets as possible, during this early development phase, we focused on integrating the two biggest datasets: the PPMI and the ProBAND (Malek et al., 2015). For consistency with the coding used in the CPP, these two datasets will, from here on, be respectively referred to as PD-1000 and PD-1003. The combination of these two datasets contained almost as many subjects as all the others combined. This allowed for the best trade-off in the amount of data to train the model against the amount of time to harmonize the data in the different datasets. This resulted in a preliminary dataset of about 4000 subjects. The only subjects to be excluded were those with no data for the specific outcome variable to be predicted in this specific model (for instance, for the model predicting dyskinesia, no subjects were included for whom dyskinesia was not reported in the dataset). Apart from this, no further inclusion/exclusion criteria were applied.

8.2.2 Data pre-processing

First, the quality of the data was checked by visually inspecting the distributions occurring for the features that were planned to be incorporated into the model. Extreme, unrealistic values (for instance, age being over 200 years) were removed and treated as non-numbers, the same as with any missing data. As an extra step of outlier detection, any values distanced 4 standard deviations away from their respective feature means were removed. Fuzzy string-matching methods were employed to correct for different misspelled entries and match them to a single value.

Our developed models up until now have mainly been random forests, which are naturally able to handle NaN values and thus require no imputation of any kind. If we move on to other models that do not possess this property, imputation methods will be used to infer the missing values, for example, using the rest of the features. Since there is typically a class imbalance between people who experience dyskinesia and those who don't, we employed a class-weighted loss every time we train our model. In addition, confusion matrices and ROC curves are used to derive metrics such as ROC-AUC to inspect whether the trained model is overly sensitive to only one of the classes.

Until now, the first focus has been on pre-processing the data and achieving an initial baseline performance for the model. In the next steps of improving the model, bias, and fairness will be of major interest. Methods such as PROBAST (Wolff et al., 2019) will be used to perform a risk of bias assessment on the dataset. In addition, the performance of the trained model will be evaluated across multiple subsets of subjects, divided by features such as age, gender, or race to assess which biases are present in the model at any given time and how they can be addressed (see Section 2 for more information on bias assessment and fairness). Until now, fairness has not really been an issue, as we are still optimizing the model to obtain a good baseline performance. Once a satisfying performance has been obtained, we will assess the model performance across multiple groups based on age, gender, race (please also refer to Section 2 of this deliverable), to assess which biases could be present in the model and whether they need explicit methods to be addressed.

8.2.3 Prediction models

Feature inclusion was based on 3 distinct sources: a) an extensive state of the art (SoA) review (please refer to deliverable *D2.3 Initial report on domain review and datasets*), b) a consensus among the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (KCL, FIN, CHUT, TUD) to ensure that the model is clinically informed by expert opinions and c) data availability in the PPMI portal (IDA-LONI). These include:

- Demographic data: Age at study enrolment (years), gender (M/F/X), BMI (kg/cm²)
- Temporal data: Age at PD diagnosis (years), Time passed since diagnosis (years)
- Test results: Hoehn-Yahr stage, UPDRS I,II,III score, ON/OFF state, Semantic verbal fluency test
- Medicinal data: Levodopa dosage (mg/day), classes of taken medication*
- Genetic data: Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) for PD-associated genes (see below)

* To include the medicines taken in the model, six classes of medication are defined: (1) Levodopa (2) Dopamine agonists (3) MAO-B inhibitors (4) COMT inhibitors and (5) Amantadine (6) Other. This classification is based on input of the AI-PROGNOSIS clinical experts (KCL, FIN, CHUT, TUD). Whether medicines belonging to any of these classes is taken by the subject is indicated by a binary indicator variable for each class. The combination of the above medications is modelled as having 2 or more of the mentioned classes.

Multiple datasets in the Integrated Database contain genetic information. Genetic information includes the genotype of each individual for several genetic variants, e.g., single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), the most common type of genetic variation among people. In the first step, the representative correlated SNPs of interest are extracted from the whole dataset. Then the association between the extracted SNPs and the effects of interest are tested with a random forest method. Based on the feature importance of this forest, a selection of a minimal set of genetic loci is performed. For the *COMT* gene, for instance, this procedure leads to the inclusion of 5 SNPs of interest, mentioning the number of the reference/mutant allele (0, 1, or 2) in the model. It could be homozygous for the "reference" allele (0), heterozygous (having one of each of the "reference" and "alternative" alleles (1)) or homozygous for the "alternative" allele (2). So far, only the *COMT* gene has been included as it has a known impact on dyskinesias, but other genes will be analysed in the future as well.

Two different paradigms are considered in the prediction of the side-effects.

- **Per-subject paradigm:** considers only a single visit per subject. To this end, for each subject who ever experiences dyskinesia, the study's last visit before the dyskinesia occurred is included in the dataset. For each subject who never experienced any dyskinesia, the study's last visit is included. From each subject's single visit we predicted whether the subject belongs to the dyskinesia group or not (Leal et al., 2023).
- **Per-visit paradigm:** predicts the occurrence of dyskinesias in each individual visit, based on the data collected during the *previous visit* and the elapsed time between these two visits. In contrast to the previous paradigm, this means varying medications, dosages and test scores can be included in the model for a more fine-grained analysis. The challenge however is that this paradigm exacerbates the class imbalance already present in the dataset. As subjects typically tend to only experience side-effects after prolonged duration of the disease, this dataset is mostly consisted of visits without dyskinesias. In this paradigm, each visit from each subject is considered as one datapoint.

The outcome of the predictive models is reported in terms of probability distributions. ROC curves are produced to display the sensitivity - specificity trade-off, allowing for an appropriate

threshold to be chosen post-hoc. The criterion used to optimise the model against is the area under the ROC curve (ROC-AUC).

8.2.4 Analytical methods

The models currently used for prediction are random forests (RF) due to (1) their straightforward handling of missing data, (2) the ease of extracting feature importances from them, and (3) their strong generalization properties. Training and hyperparameter optimization occurs through stratified 10-fold cross-validation, with the folds-consisting of the data of disjoint sets of subjects, preventing overfitting and ensuring generalizability to new subjects. The continuous features of the training set are standardised as to have zero mean and unit standard deviation, while the discrete features are left unstandardised. At test time, the learned standardisation of the training set is then applied to the test set. The considered hyperparameters consist of several standard settings for RF (depth of the decision trees, number of estimators, number of features used per decision tree). The hyperparameter setting that leads to the highest 10-fold cross-validation performance, as measured by average ROC-AUC across the folds, is then selected. Finally, the model is re-trained on the full training dataset using the selected hyperparameters.

Training versus evaluation

Evaluation of the models happens on a randomly selected, held-out test set for each dataset in the CPP, with care taken that test subjects are involved in neither the training nor validation sets. The cross-validation procedure described above is thus only intended for hyperparameter optimization, not for assessing model performance. At this stage, the features and outcome variable distribution are similar for training and testing data as they originate from the same dataset, and care is taken that both sets contain a similar ratio of dyskinesia versus non-dyskinesia subjects. Due to the presence of multiple datasets in the CPP, it will also be possible in a later stage to build a single model based on a few datasets and evaluate it on others with potentially very different data distributions, ensuring maximal generalizability of the model across multiple heterogeneous study circumstances. As for now, a single model is still trained per dataset.

8.3 Results

8.3.1 Participants

The number of participants and their degree of participation varies among datasets. **Figure 8.1** illustrates the participation degree of the subjects for the two CPP datasets currently employed, the PD-1000 and PD-1003. Note that in both graphs, only subjects whose dyskinesia status is reported in the study are included. The figure reveals that (1) there is a significant class imbalance between subjects with and without dyskinesia and (2) the proportion of subjects experiencing dyskinesia's increases as the study proceeds.

8.3.2 Model development

The outcome variable of the model is the occurrence of dyskinesia in the next visit, based on the data of the subject and the current visit and the number of days between the current and the next visit. As mentioned in Section 8.2.3, a distinction is made between the “per-visit” setting, i.e., samples consist of every visit of every subject, and the “per-subject” setting, i.e. samples consist of each subject’s last visit before dyskinesia occurs, or their last recorded visit if this never occurred at all. **Table 8.1** summarizes the participation statistics of each of these settings for both datasets.

Figure 8.1 Subject participation and dyskinesia occurrence for the two CPP datasets currently under analysis. Both graphs only include subjects whose dyskinesia status was reported in the dataset.

Table 8.1 Participation and dyskinesia statistics for each dataset and prediction framework

Dataset	Paradigm	Number of datapoints	Number of dyskinesia
PD-1000	Per-visit	7707	1827
PD-1000	Per-subject	1055	441
PD-1003	Per-visit	6409	903
PD-1003	Per-subject	1954	525

8.3.3 Model specification

As previously mentioned, the current prediction models are focused on random forests. Development took place in Python 3.9, using the *scikit-learn* library for the model, *pandas* for the pre-processing of the data and *matplotlib* for data visualization. At the end of the analysis, the developed source code will be made publicly available. The full pipeline in Python proceeds as follows. Data is extracted from the dataset, with some composite features being calculated. For instance, total UPDRS_III scores per visit are computed by summing all the relevant entries per visit, or BMI is calculated by dividing the weight in kilograms by the length in centimetres squared. The subjects are randomly assigned to the training or test set with an 80/20 split. Then, scikit-learn's StandardScaler is fitted on the training data and applied to the training and test data. Hyperparameter optimization and model fitting happen through feeding a RandomForestClassifier (with the class weight parameter set to 'balanced') to the GridSearchCV, which selects the best model based on 10-fold cross-validation and ROC-AUC as a metric, selecting from the hyperparameters of **Table 8.2**. The model is then automatically re-fitted to the full training data with these hyperparameter settings. Evaluation of the test set is then performed with this model.

Table 8.2 Hyperparameter search space for the dyskinesia prediction RF model.

Parameter name	Meaning	Values
n_estimators	Number of decision trees	[100,200,1000]

max_depth	Maximum depth of each decision tree	[2,4,5,10]
max_features	Maximum proportion of features per tree	[0.25,0.50,0.75,1]
min_samples_leaf	Minimum number of samples for each node to be a leaf	[1,3,5,10]

8.3.4 Model performance

ROC curves computed on the independent test sets for our current models in the per-visit paradigm are shown in **Figure 8.2** and **Figure 8.4** for dataset PD-1000 and PD-1003 respectively. In addition, the feature importance extracted from RF (as computed by mean decrease in impurity) is illustrated in **Figure 8.3** and **Figure 8.5**. The same plots for the per-subject paradigm are shown in **Figure 8.7** and **Figure 8.9**.

Figure 8.2 PD-1000, per visit paradigm

Figure 8.3 PD-1000, per visit paradigm

Figure 8.4 PD-1003, per visit paradigm

Figure 8.5 PD-1003, per visit paradigm

Figure 8.6 PD-1000, per-subject paradigm

Figure 8.7 PD-1000, per-subject paradigm

Figure 8.8 PD-1003, per-subject paradigm

Figure 8.9 PD-1003, per-subject paradigm

8.4 Discussion

8.4.1 Interpretation

In the per-visit paradigm, the AUC is similar between the two datasets, around 0.78. The most relevant predictors are found to be the age at PD diagnosis, time passed since then, and levodopa dosage, which is in line with the findings in the literature (Leal et al., 2023). For both models, the presence of medication class 4, i.e., COMT inhibitors appears to be a relevant contribution as well (weight of Medclass4 in Figure 8.3, **Figure 8.5** and **Figure 8.7**), which is in line with the predictions of the clinical partners of the consortium. Future research will involve investigating the role of these COMT inhibitors and for which subject characteristics they end up playing the largest role in the prediction. When it comes to assessing the contribution of medication however, it will be essential to separate correlation from causation. For instance, amantadine is typically prescribed to PD patients suffering from dyskinesia to reduce their effect. However, because of amantadine's large prevalence among the dyskinesia population compared to the non-dyskinesia population, the model can pick up on this bias to consider it as a risk factor instead. Thus, the medicinal risk factors will always need to be carefully interpreted through consideration with the clinical partners. The genetic information

on the other hand, contributes a surprisingly small amount of predictive power, which will be further investigated.

In the per-subject paradigm, a shift occurs. While the performance of the PD-1000 dataset slightly increases, the performance of the PD-1003 sharply drops. Why this is the case is currently still being investigated. It can be argued that the per-subject case is an easier task than the per-visit, because the model does not need to be able to handle the large number of visits where no dyskinesia needs to be predicted (about 90% of the cases). On the other hand, less training data is available in this paradigm, making it harder to learn a good model.

Our best baseline to assess how well we can expect these models to perform is the work of Leal et al. In this work, with the same per-subject paradigm discussed here, AUC reached 0.85 on average on the PPMI dataset, which is similar to the performance of our model on the PD-1000 and employs a similar set of features. However, this performance score is greater of the PD-1003 performance by a large margin. How to bridge this gap is the next objective of our current research.

Furthermore, as a next step, we aim to investigate whether increasing the sample size (by including more training data for a single model through combining the datasets) could increase the model's predictive power and generalizability. In addition, investigations in the literature to identify more potential features of interest will continue, while also performing ablation studies to arrive at a minimal number of features to perform prediction with.

Finally, when sufficiently predictive models are achieved, we can analyse the effect of medications under different patient characteristics, as well as the combinations of different medications. To do so, we will compare the predictions of the model with and without the medication of interest for different subgroups of the subjects, identifying the subject characteristics for which the medicines have the highest (and lowest) risk of side-effects.

8.4.2 Limitations

The models being presented here are currently still in development, so they are still limited in the predictive performance they can achieve, and the number of potential features investigated. In addition, separate models are being trained for the separate datasets, although pre-processing, the training procedure and hyperparameter optimization for each of them happens in the same way. Eventually, a single model will be trained and evaluated on the different datasets. Finally, only two of the datasets in the integrated database are currently thoroughly analysed and although together they compose about half of the full number of subjects, the inclusion of more datasets will certainly improve the heterogeneity of the training data and the model's generalizability. This step is to be accomplished in the final version of the predictive models (D3.4).

The scope of the predicted outcomes of interest at this moment is limited to the occurrence of dyskinesias. Once the modelling approach has been established for this specific side effect, it can be repurposed towards others, such as dopamine dysregulation and hallucinations and psychosis. These outcomes have been chosen because they are known side-effects to occur in PD-patients, not only caused by the disease itself, but by the interaction of the disease with the typical medication taken by these patients, especially in patients that are at early stage of the disease. In the future, more primary outcomes such as progression of the disease as measured by MDS-UPDRS scores will be modelled as well.

8.4.3 Usability of the model in the context of current care

Due to the usage of random forests, the models naturally lend themselves well towards missing data, although we currently have no analysis on the impact on the predictive power. Due to the stage of their development, the usage of the models is not yet intended for clinical practice and requires a Python virtual environment, a Jupyter notebook and data provided as Pandas Dataframes. Before taking steps towards the practical applications of these models in clinical practice, extensive work first needs to be performed on feature selection, modelling in general and robustness and fairness analysis.

9 Open science

9.1 Data sharing

Data used to develop and evaluate PD risk estimation models were obtained from the PPMI website (<https://www.ppmi-info.org>) after a formal data access application.

9.2 Code sharing

All codes supporting the findings of this study will be made openly available after publishing the results of the current deliverable in peer reviewed journals.

10 Conclusions

The key takeaways of the current report are:

- The objective of this multi-study report was to integrate genetic, clinical, and digital biomarker data across different datasets to develop predictive models for PD risk estimation, progression prediction, and medication response evaluation.
- The project efficiently harmonised the PPMI dataset into a unified structure into an OMOP common data model, setting the ground for further harmonisation practices, once the rest of the AI-PROGNOSIS identified datasets are accessed.
- Preliminary predictive models demonstrate strong potential in identifying PD risk, progression markers and medication induced adverse symptoms, highlighting the value of contributing factors, such as wearable device data (particularly for the PD risk estimation), sociodemographic factors and genetic variants.
- AI-PROGNOSIS prioritises trustworthy AI principles, such as bias mitigation and model explainability ensuring ethical and transparent AI application. These principles will be further implemented in the final version of predictive modelling in PD.
- Limitations were identified that were common among the three models, such as dataset heterogeneity and missing values, metrics and labels. Although these limitations were mitigated through advanced pre-processing techniques, additional efforts are planned to take place in the final version of predictive modelling in PD.
- In the same vein, future work will incorporate larger datasets, optimising models and validating findings in clinical settings to further improve their utility for early PD diagnosis and continuous disease monitoring and management. The final version of the predictive models will also include metrics of generalisation, such as the C-index.

References

- Abu Manneh, R., Chairta, P. P., Mitsi, E., Loizidou, M. A., Georgiou, A. N., Christou, Y. P., Pantzaris, M., Zamba-Papanicolaou, E., & Hadjisavvas, A. (2022). Genetic Study of Early Onset Parkinson's Disease in Cyprus. *Int J Mol Sci*, 23(23). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms232315369>
- Beach, P., & McKay, J. L. (2024). Longitudinal prevalence of neurogenic orthostatic hypotension in the idiopathic Parkinson Progression Marker Initiative (PPMI) cohort. *Auton Neurosci*, 253, 103173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autneu.2024.103173>
- Berg, D., Postuma, R. B., Adler, C. H., Bloem, B. R., Chan, P., Dubois, B., Gasser, T., Goetz, C. G., Halliday, G., Joseph, L., Lang, A. E., Liepelt-Scarfone, I., Litvan, I., Marek, K., Obeso, J., Oertel, W., Olanow, C. W., Poewe, W., Stern, M., & Deuschl, G. (2015). MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord*, 30(12), 1600-1611. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.26431>
- Chairta, P. P., Hadjisavvas, A., Georgiou, A. N., Loizidou, M. A., Yiangou, K., Demetriou, C. A., Christou, Y. P., Pantzaris, M., Michailidou, K., & Zamba-Papanicolaou, E. (2021). Prediction of Parkinson's Disease Risk Based on Genetic Profile and Established Risk Factors. *Genes (Basel)*, 12(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12081278>
- Fang, X., Han, D., Cheng, Q., Zhang, P., Zhao, C., Min, J., & Wang, F. (2018). Association of Levels of Physical Activity With Risk of Parkinson Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA Netw Open*, 1(5), e182421. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2018.2421>
- FitzGerald, J. J., Lu, Z., Jareonsettasin, P., & Antoniadou, C. A. (2018). Quantifying Motor Impairment in Movement Disorders. *Front Neurosci*, 12, 202. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2018.00202>
- Heinzel, S., Berg, D., Gasser, T., Chen, H., Yao, C., Postuma, R. B., & Disease, M. D. S. T. F. o. t. D. o. P. s. (2019). Update of the MDS research criteria for prodromal Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord*, 34(10), 1464-1470. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.27802>
- Iakovakis, D., Hadjidimitriou, S., Charisis, V., Bostantzopoulou, S., Katsarou, Z., & Hadjileontiadis, L. J. (2018). Touchscreen typing-pattern analysis for detecting fine motor skills decline in early-stage Parkinson's disease. *Sci Rep*, 8(1), 7663. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-25999-0>
- Kim, J. J., Vitale, D., Otani, D. V., Lian, M. M., Heilbron, K., andMe Research, T., Iwaki, H., Lake, J., Solsberg, C. W., Leonard, H., Makarious, M. B., Tan, E. K., Singleton, A. B., Bandres-Ciga, S., Noyce, A. J., Global Parkinson's Genetics, P., Blauwendraat, C., Nalls, M. A., Foo, J. N., & Mata, I. (2024). Multi-ancestry genome-wide association meta-analysis of Parkinson's disease. *Nat Genet*, 56(1), 27-36. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-023-01584-8>
- Leal, D. A. B., Dias, C. M. V., Ramos, R. P., & Brys, I. (2023). Prediction of dyskinesia in Parkinson's disease patients using machine learning algorithms. *Sci Rep*, 13(1), 22426. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-49617-w>
- Marees, A. T., de Kluiver, H., Stringer, S., Vorspan, F., Curis, E., Marie-Claire, C., & Derks, E. M. (2018). A tutorial on conducting genome-wide association studies: Quality control and statistical analysis. *Int J Methods Psychiatr Res*, 27(2), e1608. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mpr.1608>

- Mavaddat, N., Michailidou, K., Dennis, J., Lush, M., Fachal, L., Lee, A., Tyrer, J. P., Chen, T. H., Wang, Q., Bolla, M. K., Yang, X., Adank, M. A., Ahearn, T., Aittomaki, K., Allen, J., Andrulis, I. L., Anton-Culver, H., Antonenkova, N. N., Arndt, V.,...Easton, D. F. (2019). Polygenic Risk Scores for Prediction of Breast Cancer and Breast Cancer Subtypes. *Am J Hum Genet*, 104(1), 21-34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajhg.2018.11.002>
- Menza, M., Dobkin, R. D., Marin, H., & Bienfait, K. (2010). Sleep disturbances in Parkinson's disease. *Mov Disord*, 25 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), S117-122. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.22788>
- Nalls, M. A., Blauwendraat, C., Vallerga, C. L., Heilbron, K., Bandres-Ciga, S., Chang, D., Tan, M., Kia, D. A., Noyce, A. J., Xue, A., Bras, J., Young, E., von Coelln, R., Simon-Sanchez, J., Schulte, C., Sharma, M., Krohn, L., Pihlstrom, L., Siitonen, A.,...International Parkinson's Disease Genomics, C. (2019). Identification of novel risk loci, causal insights, and heritable risk for Parkinson's disease: a meta-analysis of genome-wide association studies. *Lancet Neurol*, 18(12), 1091-1102. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(19\)30320-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(19)30320-5)
- Norcliffe-Kaufmann, L., Kaufmann, H., Palma, J. A., Shibao, C. A., Biaggioni, I., Peltier, A. C., Singer, W., Low, P. A., Goldstein, D. S., Gibbons, C. H., Freeman, R., Robertson, D., & Autonomic Disorders, C. (2018). Orthostatic heart rate changes in patients with autonomic failure caused by neurodegenerative synucleinopathies. *Ann Neurol*, 83(3), 522-531. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.25170>
- Pitz, V., Makarious, M., Bandres-Ciga, S., Iwaki, H., Singleton, A., Nalls, M., Heilbron, K., & Blauwendraat, C. (2023). Analysis of rare Parkinson's disease variants in millions of people. *Res Sq*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2743857/v1>
- Schalkamp, A. K., Peall, K. J., Harrison, N. A., & Sandor, C. (2023). Wearable movement-tracking data identify Parkinson's disease years before clinical diagnosis. *Nat Med*, 29(8), 2048-2056. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-023-02440-2>
- Severson, K. A., Chahine, L. M., Smolensky, L. A., Dhuliawala, M., Frasier, M., Ng, K., Ghosh, S., & Hu, J. (2021). Discovery of Parkinson's disease states and disease progression modelling: a longitudinal data study using machine learning. *Lancet Digit Health*, 3(9), e555-e564. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(21\)00101-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(21)00101-1)
- Skrahina, V., Gaber, H., Vollstedt, E. J., Forster, T. M., Usnich, T., Curado, F., Bruggemann, N., Paul, J., Bogdanovic, X., Zulfahar, S., Olmedillas, M., Skobalj, S., Ameziane, N., Bauer, P., Csoti, I., Koleva-Alazeh, N., Grittner, U., Westenberger, A., Kasten, M.,...Group, R. S. (2021). The Rostock International Parkinson's Disease (ROPAD) Study: Protocol and Initial Findings. *Mov Disord*, 36(4), 1005-1010. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mds.28416>
- Sotirakis, C., Su, Z., Brzezicki, M. A., Conway, N., Tarassenko, L., FitzGerald, J. J., & Antoniadou, C. A. (2023). Identification of motor progression in Parkinson's disease using wearable sensors and machine learning. *NPJ Parkinsons Dis*, 9(1), 142. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-023-00581-2>
- Zanardi, A. P. J., da Silva, E. S., Costa, R. R., Passos-Monteiro, E., Dos Santos, I. O., Kruehl, L. F. M., & Peyre-Tartaruga, L. A. (2021). Gait parameters of Parkinson's disease compared with healthy controls: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sci Rep*, 11(1), 752. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-80768-2>